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**Synthetic few-cycle shadowgraphy diagnostics
in particle-in-cell codes for characterizing
laser-plasma accelerators**

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Zusammenfassung

Die Schattenbildtechnik (Shadowgraphy) ist eine Diagnostik, mit der man Mikrometer große Strukturen in Laser Plasma Beschleuniger auf Femtosekunden Zeitskalen untersuchen kann. Diese Masterarbeit beschreibt das Design und die Implementation eines in-situ Shadowgraphy-Plugins für den Particle-In-Cell Code PIconGPU.

Das C++-Plugin extrahiert den Probe Laser aus einer zeitintegrierenden Ebene in der Simulation und propagiert ihn mittels Methoden der Fourier Optik auf eine virtuelle CCD um ein synthetisches Schattenbild zu erzeugen. Aufgrund der vollständigen Modellierung der Particle-in-Cell Methode enthält der Probe Laser nach Interaktion mit dem Plasma alle Informationen, die man auch in einem experimentellen Schattenbild erwarten würde. Dieser in-situ Ansatz verhindert, dass man GB bis TB an Feld Daten auf Festplatten schreiben muss and auf rechenaufwändige Post-Processing Laufzeiten angewiesen ist, indem es die synthetischen Schattenbilder berechnet, während die PIconGPU Simulation auf einem Computercluster läuft und die Felder einfach zugänglich im Arbeitsspeicher sind.

Das in-situ Shadowgraphy-Plugin wurde erfolgreich mit einer zusätzlich gebauten Post-Processing Implementation verifiziert. Es wurde dann in Laser Wakefield Beschleuniger Simulationen genutzt, um den Effekt von verschiedenen Probe Laser Wellenlängen und Pump-Probe Verzögerungen zu untersuchen. Zusätzlich wurde der Einfluss von unterschiedlichen Fokuspositionen des virtuellen Linsensystems auf die resultierenden Schattenbilder untersucht.

Das Plugin ist eine neuartige synthetische Diagnostik, mit der man das aktuelle Verständnis der physikalischen Prozesse verbessern kann, die zu experimentellen Schattenbilder führen.

Abstract

Shadowgraphy is a diagnostic that can probe micrometer sized structures on femtosecond time scales in laser plasma accelerators. This master's thesis describes the design and implementation of an in-situ shadowgraphy plugin for the particle-in-cell code PIconGPU.

The C++-plugin extracts a probe laser out of a single time-integrating slice in the simulation and propagates it with a Fourier optics approach onto a virtual CCD to obtain synthetic shadowgrams. Since the probe laser is propagated with the particle-in-cell code itself, it contains the full laser-plasma interactions, that one would expect to see in an experimental shadowgram. The in-situ approach allows to avoid excessive disk output of many GB to TB of field data as well as the resource-intensive post-processing runtimes by directly providing the synthetic shadowgrams while the PIconGPU simulation is still running on the compute cluster and the field data is easily accessible in memory.

The in-situ shadowgraphy plugin was successfully validated with a supplementary built post-processing implementation. It was then used in laser wakefield accelerator simulations to study the effect of different probe laser wavelengths and pump-probe delays. Additionally, the impact of different focus positions of the virtual lens system on the resulting shadowgrams was examined.

The plugin is a novel synthetic diagnostic, which can help improve the current understanding of the physical processes that lead to experimental shadowgrams.

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1. Introduction

Laser wakefield accelerators (LWFA) are a type of laser plasma accelerator (LPA) that can accelerate electrons up to GeV energies on a cm-scales, which is more compact than traditional radio-frequency based accelerators, that are 100m to km large [1, 2]. In LWFAs a high intensity (~ 100 TW), short duration (~ 30 fs) laser pulse propagates through an underdense plasma $n_e < n_c$, with the critical density being $n_c = \omega^2 m_e \epsilon_0 / e^2$. This laser drives plasma waves with the ponderomotive force inside the plasma, which can accelerate electrons [3, 4]. These accelerated electron bunches have a short transversal and longitudinal extent on a μm -scale [5–8], which makes them ideal as x-ray sources [9–13] or potential drivers for free electron lasers (FEL) [14–16]. Additionally, one can use the accelerated electrons from LWFAs to drive plasma wakes themselves in a second plasma stage [17, 18]. These beam-driven accelerators are called plasma wakefield accelerators (PWFAs). PWFAs further accelerate electrons and can circumvent the dephasing limits of LWFAs and also enhance the electron beam quality [19, 20]. The acceleration processes of both LWFAs and PWFAs happen on micron and femtosecond scales and are strongly susceptible to minor changes in the acceleration setups. Thus, in order to measure the ultrafast acceleration process, well understood diagnostics with a high resolution μm - and fs-scale, a large signal-to-noise ratio and a high dynamic range are required [6, 21]. Simulations can then help to further understand the physics processes in experiments.

One useful diagnostic is shadowgraphy, where a few-cycle probe laser propagates transversely through the accelerator, is refracted by the plasma structures and then imaged onto a charge-coupled device (CCD), which then provides a vast amount of information, not only about the plasma structures, but also drive laser properties and beam charge [17, 21–26]. Shadowgraphy is used not only for LWFAs and PWFAs, but also to analyze proton accelerators that use target normal sheath acceleration (TNSA) to accelerate protons in solid density targets to MeV energies [27–30].

Shadowgraphy is a qualitative diagnostic, that can already directly be used for a rough analysis of the spatial scales of the plasma structures. However, although few-cycle probe pulses $\tau_{probe} \ll \lambda_p / c$ are used for shadowgraphy, the resulting images are still time-integrated over 10s of femtoseconds and not exact one to one position space images of the plasma. For example, the relativistic electrons in the accelerator become transparent for the probe laser. The probe pulses are also affected by Faraday rotation caused by the strong magnetic fields from the electron beam [21, 22], by the relativistic motion of the electrons that is induced by the drive laser [25] or by the ionization process [18]. Therefore, for obtaining quantitative insights synthetic diagnostics are required to fully understand the origin of different shadowgram features and thus the plasma dynamics.

The previous way of analyzing experimental shadowgrams from LWFAs and PWFAs was to run simulations with particle-in-cell codes similar to the experiments. These simulations

1. Introduction

Figure 1.1.: Synthetic shadowgram created with the in-situ plugin from PIConGPU and the corresponding plasma density as line-out plots. The trailing cavities have a longitudinal periodicity equivalent to the plasma wavelength λ_p . However, the longitudinal size of the leading cavity δ_y appears much larger in the shadowgram compared to its actual longitudinal size in the plasma density.

provide a static plasma density that could then be imported into finite difference time domain (FDTD) solvers that propagate a probe laser with the refraction caused by the density gradients through the plasma and then record it onto a virtual CCD. For hydrogen jet TNSA experiments the expansion of the jet was also modeled with a PIC simulation, which results in a static plasma density that was converted into a refractive index field and then put into ray-tracing programs to create synthetic shadowgrams [29].

However, these methods of calculating synthetic shadowgrams do not account for the fact that all plasma dynamics happen on the same femtosecond-timescale as the length of the few-cycle probe pulse. Additionally, e.g. the Faraday rotation and ionization effects are not covered by the static synthetic shadowgraphy approaches using FDTD solvers or ray-tracing programs. Recently a post-processing analysis was developed to extract a probe laser from a particle-in-cell simulation and propagate the laser through an imaging system onto a virtual CCD [31]. Since the probe laser was propagated with the particle-in-cell simulation directly through the plasma, the full laser-plasma interactions are included in the so calculated synthetic shadowgrams.

This master's thesis describes the design and implementation of such an in-situ plugin for the particle-in-cell code PIConGPU [32, 33], that creates synthetic shadowgrams as shown in fig. 1.1 with the full laser-plasma interactions based on the aforementioned post-

processing code. It also describes the implementation of a post-processing shadowgraphy method, that allows creating synthetic shadowgrams from openPMD conform files [34], which was developed as a reference implementation for the in-situ plugin. Compared to the post-processing code that applies 3D spatial Fourier transforms onto the electric and magnetic fields from a single PIC field dump to apply masks and propagate the fields and finally create the shadowgram, the in-situ approach performs a step-by-step time domain Fourier transform by recording the probe pulse passing through a single slice in the simulation. Thus, the time-integrating approach of the in-situ plugin is closer to what experimental CCDs capture, since no spatial average at some given point in time is assumed.

The post-processing analysis requires storing and loading hundreds of Gigabytes to Terabytes of field-dumps from a PIC simulation and Fourier transforming them, which requires large amounts of memory. However, the CPU-based in-situ implementation for PIConGPU Fourier transforms the electric and magnetic fields of the simulation directly in run-time and uses the fact, that modern HPC clusters provide high-performance CPUs with large amounts of memory for every GPU node, hence one does not need to store the field dumps separately on disks. Subsequently, this plugin also allows to potentially create synthetic shadowgrams for high resolution LWFA/PWFA simulations and near critical density targets, which would be excessively resource-intensive with the post-processing approach. These synthetic shadowgrams can be used to help interpret experimental shadowgrams and provide further insight in the physics processes that create those shadowgrams.

This master's thesis is organized as follows: First, I will start by describing the algorithm and implementation of the PIConGPU in-situ plugin, and then briefly introduce the post-processing implementation in comparison to the in-situ plugin. The post-processing algorithm is efficient for studying shadowgraphy as a tool, because the underlying, refracted probe laser does not need to be generated for each set of shadowgraphy parameters, like the numerical aperture, frequency filter and various window functions. The in-situ plugin on the other hand reveals its strength, when simulation data has to be produced first. Thus, and because these parameters behave equivalent in both approaches, the post-processing implementation will be used for analyzing the shadowgraphy parameters. Afterwards the in-situ plugin is validated by quantitatively comparing the time-frequency domain Fourier transformation to its expectation value and qualitatively comparing fully calculated LWFA shadowgrams to shadowgrams from the post-processing tool. Then further simulations were done with the in-situ plugin to study the effects of different probe laser wavelengths and pump-probe delays on the resulting images. Finally, I will present a theoretical approach, which creates synthetic shadowgrams with the probe laser not yet being fully propagated through the plasma structures, allowing to recreate the temporal evolution of a single shadowgram.

2. Theory of laser wakefield accelerators, shadowgraphy and Fourier optics

2.1. Laser wakefield accelerators (LWFAs)

The size of modern conventional, rf-based accelerators reaches up to multiple kilometers, because their electric field gradients are limited by the vacuum break down limit of the accelerating structures to $< 100 \text{ MVm}^{-1}$ [1]. The following section briefly introduces the laser wakefield accelerator (LWFA) as an alternative to conventional accelerators, motivate the usage of insightful diagnostics like shadowgraphy (section 2.2), as well as simulation codes like PIconGPU (section 3.1).

The idea of accelerating electrons in a plasma in LWFAs was first proposed in 1979 [35] and LWFAs have been successfully built and run since then with the development of chirped-pulse amplifiers (CPAs) [36]. LWFAs are driven by a strong, ultrashort laser with a normalized field amplitude $a_0 \gtrsim 1$ and a duration on the scale of femtoseconds [3]. The normalized field amplitude can be calculated with

$$a_0 \approx 0.85 \sqrt{\lambda^2 [\mu\text{m}] I_0 [10^{18} \text{ Wcm}^{-2}]} \quad (2.1)$$

[6], where I_0 is the peak laser intensity, which is given by the power of the laser $P = \pi r_0^2 I_0 / 2$. The plasma in LWFAs is underdense with an electron density n_e usually between 10^{23} m^{-3} to 10^{25} m^{-3} . The determining factor of the maximal electron density is the lasers frequency ω , since the laser needs to be able to penetrate the plasma. Thus, the laser's frequency must be larger than the plasma frequency $\omega > \omega_p = \sqrt{n_e e^2 / m_e \epsilon_0}$. The mentioned electron density here was chosen for commonly used high power lasers, which operate in the visible to infrared spectrum $\lambda \sim \mu\text{m}$. Ions can often be neglected in laser wakefield accelerators, their masses are much higher than the electron masses $m_{ion} \gg m_e$, which means they move much slower than the electrons and only supply a static, homogeneous background field for those fs timescales.

When the laser enters the plasma, it pushes the electrons of the plasma transversely away from the wake with the ponderomotive force, which is in the oscillation center system

$$\vec{F}_p = -c^2 \nabla(m_{\text{eff}}) \quad (2.2)$$

[37], and thus creates an electron free wake behind it. m_{eff} is the effective mass of the electrons in the laser field $m_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{1 + \vec{a}^2 / \alpha} m$ and $\vec{a} = e\vec{A} / (m_e c)$ is the general normalized field amplitude of a vector potential \vec{A} . α is 2 for a linear and 1 for circular polarized laser.

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Figure 2.1.: This figure shows the electron density of a LWFA operated in self injection regime ($a_0 = 5.0$) in gray scale with darker areas representing higher densities. The red contour lines represent the drive laser. The simulation window is copropagating with the speed of light with the drive laser. One can see, how electrons are injected into the accelerating cavity, accelerated over a few picoseconds and then ejected from the plasma. Taken from [38].

As the drive laser is propagating through the plasma, the previously displaced electrons are attracted by the strong positive charge behind the wake, which creates a round, electron-free cavity that is co-propagating with the drive laser. The electrons are then pushed away transversely from the high density region at the back of the cavity again, so that they create trailing cavities behind the first cavity, whose diameter is equal to the plasma wavelength λ_p .

Inside the first cavity are strong electric fields on the order of

$$E_0 = m_e \omega_p c / e, \quad (2.3)$$

which can reach field strengths up to GVm^{-1} [3]. Electrons that are inside the cavity are longitudinally accelerated by the fields and transversely focused, depending on which part of the cavity the electrons are in. There are many different ways of injecting the electrons into the cavity. If the drive laser intensity is strong enough $a_0 \gtrsim 3$, the first cavity will be completely evacuated (this is called the bubble-regime) and electrons at high local densities can self-inject from the back of the first cavity into the accelerating part of the cavity. Alternatively one can create a short plasma density down-ramp [17, 39] and inject electrons by rapidly enlarging the size of the first cavity which is proportional to the plasma wavelength $\lambda_p \propto n_e^{-1/2}$. Or a strong drive laser can directly inject electrons, by ionizing atoms in a not fully preionized plasma [40–42]. Finally, the last LWFA injection process that is mentioned here, is to manually inject previously accelerated electrons from a conventional accelerator directly into the accelerating part of the cavity, which will continue the acceleration process [17, 43].

Instead of a laser, one can also use electron or proton bunches to create the plasma cavities by their Lorentz contracted Coulomb fields [4, 17]. Those accelerators are then called plasma wakefield accelerators (PWFAs).

All the previously mentioned LPAs have in common, that the injection and acceleration processes are happening on short fs time-scales and small μm spatial scales. In order to obtain insight in LPA experiments to better understand the processes that happen inside the plasma, one needs diagnostics with a high temporal and spatial resolution, large signal-to-noise ratio and a high dynamic range. Additionally, simulations can help to generate further time and spatially resolved insight, which can help to interpret the experimental diagnostics.

2.2. Shadowgraphy as a diagnostic for LWFAs

Shadowgraphy is a probing diagnostic, where a well-timed, ultrashort laser pulse propagates transversely through the laser plasma accelerator. The probe laser is refracted by the plasma structures, propagates through an imaging system and finally is recorded with a CCD. The recorded image is called a shadowgram. The aim of this section is to discuss the required characteristics of the probe pulse and to describe the physics inside the plasma structures. The imaging system will be discussed in the following sections. Although the setup will be discussed with LWFAs in mind, it can easily be expanded to other types of laser plasma accelerators and plasma interactions.

Figure 2.2.: Sketch of transverse shadowgraphy-probing of an LWFA experiment.

Figure 2.2 shows a sketch of an LWFA setup using a probing laser that creates the shadowgram. The first experimental challenge in shadowgraphy is to align both lasers, since the accelerating processes happen on a fs-scale. This is achievable today by splitting the main laser of the experiment into a high intensity drive laser and a low intensity probe laser and synchronizing these correctly [44]. The accelerating cavities are moving with the speed of light c , which is equal to the velocity of the probe laser. Hence, the probe laser must be shorter than the transverse size of the plasma cavities $c\tau_{probe} < \lambda_p$ in order to obtain shadowgrams that are not washed out due to the relativistic wakefield propagation [22]. Experimentally, a laser can be shortened to such a few-cycle femtosecond pulse duration by spectral broadening, which leads to a temporal compression [23].

Now the physical processes are examined that create the signatures of the shadowgrams in the probe laser, when the probe laser propagates through the plasma. When light, that is an electromagnetic wave, enters a medium, the electrons in the medium start oscillating with the frequency of the electromagnetic wave [45]. This oscillation then emits additional electromagnetic waves with the same frequency, but with a phase delay. The incident light now interferes with the emitted light, which causes its phase velocity to decrease. The refractive index of a medium is defined by the phase velocity of light v inside the medium compared to the vacuum speed of light c :

$$\eta = \frac{c}{v} \tag{2.4}$$

If a wavefront transits from one medium with the refraction index η_1 to another medium with the refraction index η_2 under an angle α_1 , it will be redirected. This can be explained with the Huygens-Fresnel principle (eq. (2.25)), where an infinite amount of spherical waves are emitted from the interface. These secondary waves have the same frequency as the incident light, but have a wavelength dependent on the refractive index of the material,

Figure 2.3.: Snell's law. A light ray passes under the angle α_1 from one medium with the refractive index η_1 into another medium with the refractive index η_2 . The light ray is refracted at the interface with the angle $\sin(\alpha_2) = \sin(\alpha_1) \frac{\eta_1}{\eta_2}$.

leading to a redirection of the wavefront. The redirection to the emitted angle α_2 can be explained with Snell's law fig. 2.3:

$$\frac{\sin(\alpha_2)}{\sin(\alpha_1)} = \frac{\eta_1}{\eta_2} \quad (2.5)$$

The plasma structures of the laser wakefield accelerator lead to local electron density changes, which lead to a change in the local plasma frequency $\omega_p = \sqrt{n_e e^2 / m_e \epsilon_0}$, which in turn leads to different local refractive indices η [46]:

$$\eta = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_{probe}^2}} \quad (2.6)$$

The probe laser is refracted by the local refractive index gradients. One important factor about the refractive indices in relativistic media is, that they change with the velocity of the medium to

$$\eta_{rel.} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\gamma \omega_{probe}^2}} \quad (2.7)$$

with the Lorentz factor $\gamma = \sqrt{1 + \bar{p}^2 / m^2 c^2}$, where \bar{p} is the laser-cycle averaged electron momentum [47, 48]. This Lorentz factor can be understood as the relativistic increase of the electron mass.

Furthermore, one can expect diffraction patterns, if the wavelength of the probe laser is similar to the size of plasma structures. This is caused by the plasma structures acting as apertures on the laser pulse, which emit spherical waves that can interfere with each other. Theoretically it is described with the Huygens-Fresnel principle (eq. (2.25)).

Another important process, that occurs in shadowgraphy with LPAs, is Faraday rotation. Both the current $\vec{j}(\vec{r}, t)$ created by the accelerating electrons and the electric fields inside

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the plasma cavities that change over time $\epsilon_0 \partial \vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) / \partial t$ induce strong azimuthal magnetic fields \sim kT due to Ampere's law with Maxwell's addition [6, 49]

$$\nabla \times \vec{B}(\vec{r}, t) = \mu_0 \left(\vec{j}(\vec{r}, t) + \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} \right) \quad (2.8)$$

If a linearly polarized probe laser propagates through these magnetic fields, it locally rotates by the angle

$$\phi_{rot} = \frac{e}{2m_e c} \int \frac{n_e(\vec{r})}{\langle \gamma \rangle n_{cr}} \vec{B}(\vec{r}) \cdot d\vec{s} \quad (2.9)$$

[6], where n_{cr} is the critical plasma density for the wavelength of the probe laser and $\langle \gamma \rangle$ the time averaged Lorentz factor of the background plasma electrons. This Faraday rotation in shadowgraphy is a common measurement of the magnetic fields inside the plasma cavities [21, 22].

Although the probe laser has a relatively low intensity $I_{probe} \sim 10^{14} \text{ Wcm}^{-2}$ compared to the drive laser $I_{pump} \gtrsim 10^{18} \text{ Wcm}^{-2}$, it can still have effects on the plasma density itself.

After traversing the plasma, the probe laser propagates through an optical system and then recorded by a CCD. Assuming that the probe laser is propagating on the z -axis, the CCD is measuring the energy density on its image plane $\mathcal{E}(x, y, z_i)$:

$$\mathcal{E}(x, y, z_i) = \int \vec{S}(x, y, z_i; t) \vec{e}_z dt = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \int \left(\vec{E}(x, y, z_i; t) \times \vec{B}(x, y, z_i; t) \right) \vec{e}_z dt \quad (2.10)$$

$\vec{S}(x, y, z_i; t)$ is the Poynting vector at the image plane z_i , μ_0 is the vacuum permeability. The so obtained shadowgram $\mathcal{E}(x, y, z_i)$ is a time integrated image in 2D position space, that is influenced by all the physics processes that are mentioned in this section.

2.3. Fourier optics

Section 3.2 will present the implementation of a synthetic shadowgraphy plugin in the particle-in-cell code PIconGPU. Since the simulation boxes of PIC simulations typically have dimensions of $10 \mu\text{m}$ to $100 \mu\text{m}$, it is not feasible to use PIconGPU directly to simulate the propagation of the probe laser through the lens system, which is can be on the scale of meters. Hence, a different method is needed to describe the optical system, which will be Fourier optics.

Scalar wave formalism

To explain the propagation of electromagnetic waves, the scalar wave formalism is required. From Maxwell's equations, one can derive the following 2 partial differential equations for linear, homogeneous, isotropic and non-dispersive media

$$\nabla^2 \vec{E} - \frac{\eta}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (2.11)$$

$$\nabla^2 \vec{B} - \frac{\eta}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{B}}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (2.12)$$

[49, 50]. Propagation through the optical system is assumed to take place in vacuum $\eta = 1$. Note about eq. (2.11) and eq. (2.12), that the solutions for all 3 vector components E_x , E_y , E_z , B_x , B_y and B_z are independent of each other. Thus, the solutions of the differential equations each can be written as scalar, plane waves

$$\tilde{U}(x, y, z; t) = U \exp\{i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \omega t)\}. \quad (2.13)$$

with an amplitude U and the three component wavevector \vec{k} with $|\vec{k}| = \omega/c = 2\pi/\lambda = \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2 + k_z^2}$. By separation of variables

$$\tilde{U}(x, y, z; t) = U(x, y, z) \exp\{-i\omega t\}. \quad (2.14)$$

Where $U(x, y, z)$ is a complex function of space, which is sometimes called a "phasor". This can be put into eq. (2.11), resulting into the Helmholtz equation

$$\nabla^2 U(x, y, z) + k^2 U(x, y, z) = 0. \quad (2.15)$$

Propagation of the angular spectrum

To look at the propagation of this disturbance $U(x, y, z)$, I will first look at the disturbance $U(x, y, 0)$ at $z = 0$. The wave equation can also be written as a function of its angular spectrum by Fourier transforming it transversely

$$U(x, y, 0) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \iint A(k_x, k_y, 0) e^{i(k_x x + k_y y)} dk_x dk_y. \quad (2.16)$$

One can interpret this Fourier transform as a decomposition into a linear combination of $U(x, y, 0)$ into elementary functions with the form $\exp\{i(k_x x + k_y y)\}$. Those elementary functions are plane waves with the spatial frequencies k_x and k_y and they have a weighting $A(k_x, k_y, 0)$. Subsequently, one can also write the angular spectrum as a function of the disturbance with an inverse Fourier transform

$$A(k_x, k_y, 0) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \iint U(x, y, 0) e^{-i(k_x x + k_y y)} dx dy \quad (2.17)$$

Likewise one can write the disturbance at a position $z \neq 0$ as a function of its angular spectrum as in eq. (2.16) and eq. (2.17)

$$U(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \iint A(k_x, k_y, z) e^{i(k_x x + k_y y)} dk_x dk_y \quad (2.18)$$

$$A(k_x, k_y, z) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \iint U(x, y, z) e^{-i(k_x x + k_y y)} dx dy \quad (2.19)$$

$U(x, y, z)$ must satisfy the Helmholtz equation eq. (2.15). Thus, eq. (2.18) is inserted into the Helmholtz equation, leading to following differential equation

$$0 = \left(\frac{d^2}{dz^2} - k_x^2 - k_y^2 \right) A(k_x, k_y, z) + k^2 A(k_x, k_y, z) \quad (2.20)$$

$$= \frac{d^2}{dz^2} A(k_x, k_y, z) + \left(k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2 \right) A(k_x, k_y, z) \quad (2.21)$$

Figure 2.4.: Sketch of the 4f correlator with geometrical optics light rays for clarification. The 4f correlator consists of 2 lenses which are exactly 2 focal lengths f apart. The first lens performs a Fourier transform of the incoming light from the object plane at the Fourier plane in the center between both lenses. The second lens performs an inverse Fourier transform onto the image plane.

A possible solution for this differential equation is

$$A(k_x, k_y, z) = A(k_x, k_y, 0)e^{iz\sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}}. \quad (2.22)$$

This equation describes the propagation of the angular spectrum of a plane wave over the distance z . Propagating the complete angular spectrum of the disturbance is then equal to propagating the whole plane wave after it was Fourier transformed back into position space. In the propagator $\sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}$ one must be careful that $k \geq k_x^2 + k_y^2$. If this condition was not satisfied, this plane wave component would be called an evanescent wave. Furthermore, eq. (2.22) can be rewritten with $k = \omega/c$, which will be useful later on:

$$A(k_x, k_y, z) = A(k_x, k_y, 0)e^{iz\sqrt{(\frac{\omega}{c})^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}} \quad (2.23)$$

Thus, to compute the disturbance $U(x, y, z)$ can be written as a function of the angular spectrum from the disturbance at $z = 0$:

$$U(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \iint A(k_x, k_y, 0)e^{i(k_x x + k_y y + z\sqrt{(\frac{\omega}{c})^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2})} dk_x dk_y. \quad (2.24)$$

The propagation of the angular spectrum will be used in the PIConGPU in-situ plugin to propagate the extracted probe laser from the extraction plane to the object plane of the 4f correlator.

Introduction to the 4f correlator

The chosen optical system for the propagation of the probe laser onto a virtual CCD is a 4f correlator, which consists of 2 lenses that are 2 focal lengths apart as in fig. 2.4, with geometrical light rays to hint at the mirroring properties of the lens system. One focal length in front of the first lens is the object plane of the optical system, one focal length behind the second lens is the image plane, where the shadowgram will be computed. The

Figure 2.5.: Huygens-Fresnel principle. Light is emitted from the aperture Σ on the left-hand side in the (x, y) -plane to the parallel (u, v) -plane on the right hand side.

4f correlator is a mathematically simple system, yet it is also a complete imaging system [50, 51].

In order to properly explain the 4f correlator, it will be disassembled into its components. First the Huygens-Fresnel principle and the ensuing Fresnel diffraction integral will be considered, which are important parts in describing the general propagation of the light through the 4f correlator. The Fresnel diffraction integral describes the converging and diverging waves between the lenses and the paraxial approximation of those integrals will also be used in describing the propagation of the light from the object plane to the first lens and from the second lens to the image plane. Then the quadratic phase factors that originate from the lenses will be discussed. Subsequently, the full optical system will be analyzed by describing the light propagation directly from the lens to the focal position, then from the object plane through the lens to the focal position and finally through the complete optical system.

Fresnel diffraction integral

The Huygens-Fresnel principle states that spherical waves are emitted at every point of a diffracting aperture Σ in the plane (x, y) and the waves interfere at each point in the (u, v) -plane (fig. 2.5).

$$U(u, v) = \frac{z}{i\lambda} \iint_{\Sigma} U(x, y) \frac{e^{ikr}}{r^2} dx dy \quad (2.25)$$

r is the distance between the point in the (u, v) -plane and the points that lie in the (x, y) -plane.

$$r = \sqrt{z^2 + (u - x)^2 + (v - y)^2} \quad (2.26)$$

$$\approx z \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(u - x)^2}{z^2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(v - y)^2}{z^2} \right) \quad (2.27)$$

In the second step a paraxial approximation is applied, where $(u - x)^2 \ll z^2$ and $(v - y)^2 \ll z^2$. Next this Taylor expansion is put into eq. (2.25). The small, transverse spatial vector

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summands are dropped in the denominator of $1/r^2$. However, they are important in the phase-term of the exponential function, since minor fluctuations in the phase can lead to vastly different outcomes in the resulting images.

$$U(u,v) = \frac{1}{i\lambda z} \iint_{\Sigma} U(x,y) e^{ikz \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(u-x)^2}{z^2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(v-y)^2}{z^2}\right)} dx dy \quad (2.28)$$

$$= \frac{1}{i\lambda z} e^{ikz} \iint_{\Sigma} U(x,y) e^{\frac{ik}{2z} ((u-x)^2 + (v-y)^2)} dx dy \quad (2.29)$$

The resulting amplitude of the disturbance $U(u,v)$ is proportional to a factor $1/(i\lambda z)$. The factor $1/i$ represents a $\pi/2$ phase shift, that will be dropped from now on since it is constant. Equation (2.29) can also be rewritten by expanding the binomial formulas in the exponent.

$$U(u,v) = \frac{1}{\lambda z} e^{ik(z + \frac{1}{2z}(u^2+v^2))} \iint_{\Sigma} \left[U(x,y) e^{i\frac{k}{2z}(x^2+y^2)} \right] e^{-i\frac{k}{z}(ux+vy)} dx dy \quad (2.30)$$

Both eq. (2.29) and eq. (2.30) are called the Fresnel diffraction integral. These are valid in the near-field diffraction regime, that is the sizes of the apertures are small compared to the distances between the apertures. The rewriting in eq. (2.30) illustrates that the integral can be understood as a Fourier transform of the incident waves with additional phase factors.

Quadratic phase modulation from lenses

The next paragraph describes the phase delay $U(x,y) = U'(x,y)e^{i\phi(x,y)}$ introduced by a lens in the (x,y) plane. The thin lens approximation is used, which means that the thickness of the lens Δz is ignored. $U(x,y)$ is the light on the right hand side of the lens, $U'(x,y)$ is the incident light on the left hand side. The phase can be written as a function of its refractive index n , its maximum width Δ_0 and its thickness function $\Delta(x,y)$ as

$$\phi(x,y) = kn\Delta(x,y) + k[\Delta_0 - \Delta(x,y)]. \quad (2.31)$$

Due to the thin lens approximation the emitted light is approximately at the same coordinates (x,y) as it's entering it. The thickness function is given by

$$\Delta(x,y) = \Delta_0 - R_l \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2 + y^2}{R_l^2}}\right) + R_r \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2 + y^2}{R_r^2}}\right) \quad (2.32)$$

[50]. R_l and R_r are the radii of the lens on the left hand side and on the right hand side, and Δ_0 is the constant width of the lens. In the usual sign conventions R_l is positive and R_r is negative for convex lenses. The square roots can be expanded with the paraxial approximation $\sqrt{1 - (x^2 + y^2)/R_l^2} \approx 1 - (x^2 + y^2)/2R_l^2$ and $\sqrt{1 - (x^2 + y^2)/R_r^2} \approx 1 - (x^2 + y^2)/2R_r^2$, which is possible if the lens is wide compared to the input size and the light is incident in the center of the lens. This reduces the thickness function to

$$\Delta(x,y) = \Delta_0 - \frac{x^2 + y^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_l} - \frac{1}{R_r} \right), \quad (2.33)$$

Figure 2.6.: Propagation of light from an object plane over the distance z through a lens to its focal position over the distance f .

where the constant phase shift caused by Δ_0 will be ignored from now on, since this is independent of the coordinate on the lens. This can be inserted into eq. (2.31).

$$\phi(x,y) = -k(n-1)\frac{x^2+y^2}{2}\left(\frac{1}{R_l} - \frac{1}{R_r}\right) \quad (2.34)$$

The radii and refractive index are physical properties of the lens, which are usually condensed into the focal length f :

$$\frac{1}{f} = (n-1)\left(\frac{1}{R_l} - \frac{1}{R_r}\right). \quad (2.35)$$

Therefore, lenses add a quadratic phase shift, that is given by

$$U_l(x,y) = U'_l(x,y) \exp\left\{-i\frac{k}{2f}(x^2+y^2)\right\}. \quad (2.36)$$

Propagation through a lens to its focal position

Equation (2.30) and eq. (2.36) can be used to describe light propagation through the lens (x,y) to the focal plane (u,v) (see the right side of fig. 2.6).

$$U_f(u,v) = \frac{e^{ikf}}{\lambda f} e^{i\frac{k}{2f}(u^2+v^2)} \iint [U(x,y)] e^{-i\frac{k}{f}(ux+vy)} dx dy \quad (2.37)$$

In this equation, the finite size of the aperture Σ is neglected, assuming that the input is smaller than the aperture. The quadratic phases $\exp\{ik(x^2+y^2)/2f\}$ from the Fresnel diffraction integral and from the lens cancel out. This shows that the light in the focal plane (u,v) is equal to the Fourier transform of the light on the left hand side of the lens with a quadratic prefactor.

$$U_f(u,v) = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda f} e^{ikf} e^{i\frac{k}{2f}(u^2+v^2)} \mathcal{F}\{U(x,y)\} \quad (2.38)$$

$$= \frac{k}{f} e^{ikf} e^{i\frac{k}{2f}(u^2+v^2)} A_l\left(\frac{ku}{f}, \frac{kv}{f}\right) \quad (2.39)$$

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It was shown that the transverse spatial Fourier transform of a disturbance is the angular spectrum and it is known, how to propagate this angular spectrum from the object plane of the 4f correlator to the front of the first lens (eq. (2.22)):

$$A_l(k_x, k_y) = A_o(k_x, k_y) e^{iz\sqrt{k^2 - (k_x)^2 - (k_y)^2}}. \quad (2.40)$$

For a brief demonstration purpose, the distance between the object plane (fig. 2.6) and the first lens will be called z is arbitrary for the moment and will be set to f a few steps further on. The propagation can be further simplified with the paraxial approximation $\sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2} \approx k \left(1 - k_x^2/2k^2 - k_y^2/2k^2\right)$:

$$A_l(k_x, k_y) = A_o(k_x, k_y) \exp \left\{ izk \left(1 - \frac{k_x^2}{2k^2} - \frac{k_y^2}{2k^2}\right) \right\} \quad (2.41)$$

¹. This can be inserted into eq. (2.39) to derive the light at the Fourier plane as a function of the light from the object plane:

$$U_f(u, v) = \frac{k}{f} e^{ikf} e^{i\frac{k}{2f}(u^2+v^2)} e^{iz\left(k - \frac{1}{2k}\left(\frac{uk}{f}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{2k}\left(\frac{vk}{f}\right)^2\right)} A_o\left(\frac{uk}{f}, \frac{vk}{f}\right) \quad (2.42)$$

$$= \frac{k}{f} e^{ik(f+z)} e^{i\frac{k}{2f}(u^2+v^2)} e^{-i\frac{z}{2k}\left(\left(\frac{uk}{f}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{vk}{f}\right)^2\right)} A_o\left(\frac{uk}{f}, \frac{vk}{f}\right) \quad (2.43)$$

$$= \frac{k}{f} e^{ik(f+z)} e^{i\frac{k}{2f}(u^2+v^2)} e^{-i\frac{zk}{2f^2}(u^2+v^2)} A_o\left(\frac{uk}{f}, \frac{vk}{f}\right) \quad (2.44)$$

$$= \frac{k}{f} e^{ik(f+z)} e^{i\frac{k}{2f}\left(1 - \frac{z}{f}\right)(u^2+v^2)} A_o\left(\frac{uk}{f}, \frac{vk}{f}\right) \quad (2.45)$$

So if $z = f$, the disturbance at the focal plane is equal to the exact Fourier transform of the light at the object plane with a constant phase that comes from the propagation over the distance $2f$:

$$U_f(u, v) = \frac{k}{f} e^{2ikf} A_o\left(\frac{uk}{f}, \frac{vk}{f}\right). \quad (2.46)$$

Using spatial filters in the 4f correlator

The propagation from the focal plane to the image plane works equivalent to the propagation from object plane to the image plane. The quadratic phases from the Fresnel propagation and the lens cancel out and the second lens performs a Fourier transform of the image at the focal plane, which is the angular spectrum. Thus, the 4f correlator calculates the Fourier transform of a Fourier transform of the image at the object plane, which can be understood with the relation $\mathcal{F}\{\mathcal{F}\{f(x)\}\} = f(-x)$. Furthermore, one can normalize the spatial coordinates of the Fourier transform in the angular spectrum $\xi' \rightarrow \sqrt{k/f}\xi$ and $\eta' \rightarrow \sqrt{k/f}\eta$ to remove the k/f -prefactor. The disturbance at the image plane as a function of the disturbance at the object plane is:

$$U_i(\xi, \eta) = e^{4ikf} U_o(-\xi, -\eta). \quad (2.47)$$

¹It is also possible to obtain this propagation by Fourier transforming the Fresnel diffraction equation eq. (2.30).

Figure 2.7.: The parts of the light where the wave vector \vec{k} lies outside the cone is removed by the numerical aperture that is implemented in eq. (2.49).

The constant phase factor comes from the propagation over the whole distance of the 4f correlator and can be neglected, because a constant phase has no physical meaning. This result is equivalent to the geometrical optics approach in fig. 2.4. The 4f correlator is mirroring an image from the object plane to the image plane by simply flipping it.

A circular mask with the radius $D/2$ is defined as:

$$\mathcal{M}(u,v) = \begin{cases} 1, & \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} < \frac{D}{2} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.48)$$

This mask can be put into the center between both lenses, the focal plane, to remove Fourier components of the incident light. Due to the convolution theorem, this mask can be multiplied directly onto eq. (2.46):

$$U_f(u,v) = \frac{k}{f} e^{2ikf} \mathcal{M}(u,v) A_o \left(\frac{uk}{f}, \frac{vk}{f} \right). \quad (2.49)$$

The spatial mask eq. (2.48) can be rewritten by using the transverse wave-vectors $k_x = uk/f$ and $k_y = vk/f$. This will show, how spatial filters in a 4f-correlator can be used to apply operations in Fourier space.

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} &< \frac{D}{2} \\ \rightarrow \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2} &< \frac{Dk}{f2} \\ \rightarrow \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2} &< \text{NA} \frac{\omega}{c} \end{aligned}$$

In the last step the definition of the numerical aperture $\text{NA} = D/2f$ was used. The numerical aperture removes the light, where the perpendicular k vector $k_{\perp} = \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2}$ is too large compared to the length of the k vector, see fig. 2.7. This is a useful tool to remove e.g. side scattered light from the drive laser in LWFA simulations.

In conclusion it was shown in this section, that the 4f-correlator simply mirrors a disturbance from the object plane to the image plane. The first lens Fourier transform the image to the focal plane, the second lens acts another Fourier transformation to the image plane, flipping the image. Thus, it is possible to apply spatial filters, that work equivalently to Fourier space filters, in the center between both lenses.

3. Implementation of an in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic in PIConGPU

3.1. Particle-in-cell code PIConGPU

This section briefly describes how the particle-in-cell code PIConGPU [32, 33] works, how plugins are integrated into the main loop of the simulation code and what makes it suitable for in-situ shadowgraphy calculations. Particle-in-cell codes are finite-difference-time-domain (FDTD) methods, that include particles in addition to the fields. As usual for FDTD codes, PIConGPU discretizes the electric and magnetic fields on a staggered Yee grid (fig. 3.2) to solve Maxwell’s equations as shown in fig. 3.1. The particles lie within a continuous phase space, but due to the large amounts of particles that are necessary for plasma simulations, particles are grouped in so called macro-particles, that sample the 6D distribution function of the particles [52].

A particle-in-cell code loops through discretized time steps and, first, calculates the electric and magnetic fields for the current time step. Then it computes the Lorentz force $\vec{F} = q(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B})$ and pushes the macro-particles according to the force. The moving particles generate a current, which in turn generates an electric field, that induces a magnetic field in the next time step.

Additionally, PIConGPU introduces intermediate calculations for e.g. collisions, ionization or other plugins and extension. Particularly the plugins are a strength of PIConGPU, which can be called during the main PIC loop (fig. 3.1) at each step after the fields have been computed and before the Lorentz force is computed. The plugins compute supplementary physics processes in-situ while the simulation is running to circumvent post-processing

Figure 3.1.: Schematic visualization of the 4 steps of the particle-in-cell algorithm. Taken from [38]

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Figure 3.2.: Yee offset of the E and B fields for grid index (i, j, k) .

calculations. Post-processing calculations are also possible with the openPMD output from PIConGPU, but are generally slower to perform and require storing terabytes of data. Furthermore, PIConGPU is parallelizable on many GPUs, which means that it can be used to simulate very large volumes or complex systems, like high resolution Laser-Wakefield or large ion acceleration simulations [53]. For LWFA-like simulations a moving window is introduced that co-propagates with the drive laser, which then allows for time-resolved, femtosecond insight in many phases in the acceleration process.

PIConGPU is a full 3D code with no assumed symmetry such as a rotational symmetry, meaning one can add a transverse probe-laser that propagates through the plasma structures. As long as the probe-laser wavelength is resolved by the cell-size of the simulation, it inherently acquires all the modulations that one would expect from an experimental shadowgram. This includes refraction, diffraction, Faraday rotation or the effects of the probe laser on the plasma (see section 2.2).

Figure 3.3.: Structure of the full PIConGPU plugin loop with fig. 3.4, fig. 3.5 and fig. 3.7

3.2. Numerical implementation of shadowgraphy in PIConGPU

This section describes in depth the implementation of an in-situ shadowgraphy probe extraction plugin into PIConGPU (fig. 3.3), which I developed during this thesis. It is based on the post-processing implementation from [31].

Due to the sheer possible size of the simulations, it is difficult to perform 3D Fourier transformations like the post-processing implementation. It is also not possible to perform a fast Fourier transform (FFT¹), which is a global operation, because of the domain-decomposition of electric and magnetic fields in the simulation. Instead, the plugin assumes a static slice at z_s , that is the integration plane, transverse to the probe laser.

The plugin performs a step-by-step frequency-domain discrete Fourier transform (DFT) on the electric and magnetic fields, until the probe laser has fully propagated through this integration plane. Afterwards a transverse, 2D FFT is performed to transform $\hat{E}(x, y, z_s; \omega)$ and $\hat{B}(x, y, z_s; \omega)$ into $\hat{\hat{E}}(k_x, k_y, z_s; \omega)$ and $\hat{\hat{B}}(k_x, k_y, z_s; \omega)$, which enables a propagation to the object plane of the 4f correlator $\hat{\hat{E}}(k_x, k_y, z_o; \omega)$ and $\hat{\hat{B}}(k_x, k_y, z_o; \omega)$ and an application of a numerical aperture and a frequency filter².

The image at the object plane z_o is equivalent to the image at the image plane z_i in a 4f correlator as discussed in section 2.3. This propagation mimics a change of the focal position of optical systems in experiments. If the object plane is exactly at the position of the extraction plane, the extracted laser would be exactly in focus when it is recorded. However, this propagation enables changing the object plane of the lens system and thus allows to manually set focus of the lens-system to an arbitrary position.

Finally the fields are transformed back into position-time space $\vec{E}(x, y, z_i; t)$ and $\vec{B}(x, y, z_i; t)$

¹FFT is usually used interchangeably with discrete Fourier transformation (DFT), because a FFT is a fast implementation of a DFT. But since this plugin implementation also includes a naive implementation of Fourier transform from time to frequency space additionally to FFTs to transform from position to \vec{k} space, I will always refer to the t - ω transforms with DFT and to the \vec{r} - \vec{k} with FFT in this section.

²Both the \vec{E} and \vec{B} fields are obviously still vector fields with 3 components. But I will drop the vector arrow from E and B in this section for sake of clarity, as long as no vector operations are applied to them. Additionally, it can also be seen in eq. (3.1), that the z component of the fields is dispensable for the calculations since we are only interested into the z component of the Poynting vector.

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Figure 3.4.: The first part of the plugin loop: the DFT into (x, y, ω) -space

and time integrated to obtain the energy density according to eq. (2.10).

$$\mathcal{E}(x, y, z_i) = \int \vec{S}(x, y, z_i; t) \cdot \vec{e}_z dt = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \int \left(\vec{E}(x, y, z_i; t) \times \vec{B}(x, y, z_i; t) \right) \vec{e}_z dt \quad (3.1)$$

The vector product in this equation requires all field components from $E(x, y, z_s; t)$ and $B(x, y, z_s; t)$ to have the same spatial coordinate. Due to the Yee-offset (fig. 3.2), they must first be linearly interpolated to have the same coordinate system.

Part 1: DFT of electric and magnetic field into frequency domain

The first part of the plugin is the extraction of the probe laser from the slice in the simulation at z_s and the direct Fourier transformation into frequency domain. This slice is usually positioned outside the plasma wakes, when the probe laser has already propagated through the plasma structures. It is assumed that the further propagation from the probe laser out of the homogeneous plasma does not lead to further signatures in the shadowgrams. Hence, this slice-approach allows for transversely more compact simulation boxes compared to the larger scales of the experimental setups.

The slice is spatially static, which needs to be considered in LWFA or PWFA simulations, where the moving window is usually enabled. Due to the moving window, the resulting image will be smaller in plasma wake propagation direction y by the same distance that the probe laser propagates through the simulation box in z direction from when it first enters the simulation box until it has fully propagated through the slice.

While the probe pulse is passing through the integration slice at z_s , the plugin takes the electric and magnetic field for each time-step $t \in \Delta t[0, 1, \dots, n_t - 1]$ from the slice and

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Figure 3.5.: The second part of the plugin loop: the propagation to the image plane z_i

directly performs a frequency domain DFT, until the probe laser has fully propagated through the slice:

$$\hat{E}(x, y, z_s; \omega) = \sum_t E(x, y, z_s; t) e^{i\omega t} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\hat{B}(x, y, z_s; \omega) = \sum_t B(x, y, z_s; t) e^{i\omega t}. \quad (3.3)$$

This is visualized in fig. 3.4. Δt is the passed time between plugin calls and it is assumed that n_t is even or it is enforced otherwise. The frequency domain is discretized accordingly $\omega \in 2\pi/(n_t \Delta t)[-n_t/2, -n_t/2 + 1, \dots, n_t/2 - 1]$. This procedure creates a 3D array for each field with the size (n_x, n_y, n_ω) . Since a band pass filter will be applied in the ω domain, which is centered around the probe laser's frequency $\omega_{probe} - \delta\omega < \omega < \omega_{probe} + \delta\omega$ with the bandwidth $2\delta\omega$, these arrays will use less memory than storing them in (x, y, t) -domain.

Part 2: Application of masks and propagation

After the probe pulse has been fully transformed into $(x, y, z_s; \omega)$ -space, the second part (fig. 3.5) of the plugin starts. The goal of this part is to apply a numerical aperture,

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frequency filter and propagate the fields from the integration plane z_s to the image plane z_i of the 4f correlator.

The numerical aperture mimics the experimental numerical aperture $NA = D/2f$, which is the acceptance angle of a utilized lens system. The frequency filter can be used as an equivalent to the experimental spectral acceptance range of the CCD. Furthermore, actual frequency filters are used in experiments to separate the probe laser from the drive laser. The NA and the frequency filter will be discussed in more detail in section 4.3 and section 4.4.

The numerical aperture is a mask function that depends on the perpendicular k -vector and the frequency (eq. (2.48)). In the plugin developed during this thesis, the NA and the frequency filter are merged together into the function $\mathcal{M}(k_x, k_y, \omega)$ because they behave similarly.

To be able to apply the mask and to propagate the fields, the plugin first transforms the fields into transverse k space using FFTs from the FFTW library [54].

$$\hat{E}(k_x, k_y, z_s; \omega) = \mathcal{F}\{\hat{E}(x, y, z_s; \omega)\}_{FFT} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\hat{B}(k_x, k_y, z_s; \omega) = \mathcal{F}\{\hat{B}(x, y, z_s; \omega)\}_{FFT} \quad (3.5)$$

After this step the fields are 3D arrays in (k_x, k_y, ω) -space, where the masks and a propagator by the distance Δz from the integration plane at z_s to the image plane at z_i (eq. (2.23)) can be applied:

$$\hat{E}(k_x, k_y, z_i; \omega) = \mathcal{M}(k_x, k_y, \omega) \hat{E}(k_x, k_y, z_s; \omega) e^{i\Delta z \sqrt{(\frac{\omega}{c})^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}} \quad (3.6)$$

$$\hat{B}(k_x, k_y, z_i; \omega) = \mathcal{M}(k_x, k_y, \omega) \hat{B}(k_x, k_y, z_s; \omega) e^{i\Delta z \sqrt{(\frac{\omega}{c})^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}} \quad (3.7)$$

As last step of the second plugin part the fields are transformed back into (x, y, ω) -space via inverse, transverse 2D FFTs and taking care of the normalization of the Fourier transform

$$\hat{E}(x, y, z_i; \omega) = \frac{1}{n_x n_y} \mathcal{F}\{\hat{E}(k_x, k_y, z_i; \omega)\}_{iFFT} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\hat{B}(x, y, z_i; \omega) = \frac{1}{n_x n_y} \mathcal{F}\{\hat{B}(k_x, k_y, z_i; \omega)\}_{iFFT}. \quad (3.9)$$

This second part of the plugin is generally very fast due to the effectiveness and optimization of FFTs in the FFTW library.

Part 3: Time integration of the Poynting vectors

The third and final part of the plugin loop performs a DFT back into time domain, calculates the Poynting vectors and computes the time integration to obtain the final 2D image. The required calculation of the latter time integration is derived by inserting the

Figure 3.6.: Schematic visualization of the inductive sum eq. (3.14)

definition of inverse DFTs into eq. (2.10)

$$\mathcal{E}(x, y, z_i) = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \int \left(\vec{E}(x, y, z_i; t) \times \vec{B}(x, y, z_i; t) \right) \vec{e}_z dt \quad (3.10)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\mu_0 n_i^2} \Re \left\{ \int \left(\sum_{\omega} \hat{E}(x, y, z_i; \omega) e^{-i\omega t} \times \sum_{\omega'} \hat{B}(x, y, z_i; \omega') e^{-i\omega' t} \right) \vec{e}_z dt \right\} \quad (3.11)$$

$$= \frac{\Delta t}{\mu_0 n_i^2} \Re \left\{ \sum_t \left(\sum_{\omega} \hat{E}(x, y, z_i; \omega) e^{-i\omega t} \times \sum_{\omega'} \hat{B}(x, y, z_i; \omega') e^{-i\omega' t} \right) \vec{e}_z \right\} \quad (3.12)$$

The $1/n_i^2$ here originates from normalizing the DFT and the Δt from the outer time integration. In the last step the time integration was simply discretized.

The challenge for efficiently computing eq. (3.12) lies in the frequency sums, which will result in an inefficient 3-layered loop that is $\mathcal{O}(n_{\omega}^2)$, because for most functions A_i and B_j :

$$\sum_{i=0}^n A_i \cdot \sum_{j=0}^n B_j \neq \sum_{k=0}^n A_k \cdot B_k \quad (3.13)$$

This formula can be rewritten inductively for any index n to

$$\sum_{i=0}^n A_i \cdot \sum_{j=0}^n B_j = A_n B_n + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} A_i B_n + A_n \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} B_j + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} A_i \cdot \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} B_j, \quad (3.14)$$

which is visualized in fig. 3.6.

If $n = 0$, the base case is simply $A_0 B_0$. One also keeps an off-sum for both A and B , which are equal to A_0 and B_0 respectively. For each $n > 0$, the product of the sums is equal to

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the diagonal element $A_n B_n$ plus the off-sums $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} A_i$ and $\sum_{j=0}^{n-1} B_j$ multiplied with the corresponding B_n and A_n plus the previous product of the sum $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} A_i \cdot \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} B_j$. The values A_n and B_n are added to their corresponding off-sums, before one iterates to the next $n \rightarrow n + 1$. After iterating over all n , one has obtained the product of 2 sums. This is possible if both sums have the same amount of indices and both functions don't depend on the sum index of the respective other function.

Equation (3.14) is implemented into eq. (3.12), making it a $\mathcal{O}(n_\omega)$ algorithm and thus significantly increasing the performance. So the final time integration of the E and B fields in (x, y, ω) -space at our image plane z_i is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}(x, y, z_i) = \frac{\Delta t}{\mu_0 n_t^2} \Re \left\{ \sum_t \left(\sum_{n=0}^{n_\omega} \left(\hat{E}(x, y, z_i; \omega_n) \times \hat{B}(x, y, z_i; \omega_n) e^{-i2\omega_n t} \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} \hat{E}(x, y, z_i; \omega_m) e^{-i\omega_m t} \times \hat{B}(x, y, z_i; \omega_n) e^{-i\omega_n t} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \hat{E}(x, y, z_i; \omega_n) e^{-i\omega_n t} \times \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} \hat{B}(x, y, z_i; \omega_m) e^{-i\omega_m t} \right) \right) \vec{e}_z \left. \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

Alternatively the third part of the algorithm is shown in fig. 3.7.

The implementation and the effects of the numerical aperture are further discussed in section 4.3 with the help of the post-processing implementation. The band-pass filter will be discussed with the post-processing implementation in section 4.4. Additionally, the whole plugin loop requires 4 Fourier transform (2 2D spatial, 2 1D time-frequency domain) which all contain jump discontinuities caused by either the limited simulation box size or the NA or frequency filter. This leads to ringing effects in the final shadowgram. Thus, section 4.2 will discuss the effect of different window functions to reduce the ringing artifacts in the final shadowgram.

In summary, it has been shown in this section, how the in-situ plugin for PIConGPU is designed and implemented. This workflow is more efficient, and it enables higher resolution synthetic shadowgrams than the post-processing workflow that the plugin is based on.

Figure 3.7.: The third part of the plugin loop: time integration of the Poynting vector

3.3. Reference implementation of a post-processing tool

Furthermore, I have also implemented a post-processing method in a python script. This method extracts a probe laser from a single data dump of the electric and magnetic fields from openPMD conform output [34]. It was already validated against the original implementation [31].

Four goals are pursued with the development of this post-processing tool. First, familiarize myself with the computation of synthetic shadowgrams. Second, provide a post-processing tool for the calculation of synthetic shadowgrams for all simulation codes producing openPMD conform output. Third, test and verify specifics of the method, such as numerical aperture or frequency filters, in a reduced environment compared to the full PIconGPU software stack. Fourth, validate the in-situ plugin by comparing shadowgrams from the same simulation.

Compared to the in-situ plugin, the post-processing implementation works by taking the volume of the simulation at one specific time step t_s , that includes the probe laser after it has propagated through the plasma wake. The post-processing method then performs a 3D spatial Fourier transform on the electric and magnetic fields $\vec{E}(x, y, z; t_s)$ and $\vec{B}(x, y, z; t_s)$, to obtain those fields in \vec{k} -space $\vec{E}(k_x, k_y, k_z; t_s)$ and $\vec{B}(k_x, k_y, k_z; t_s)$. Then a numerical aperture and a frequency filter are applied to those fields, similarly to the in-situ implementation, but with a third spatial wave-vector $k_z = \sqrt{\omega^2/c^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}$ instead of the frequency ω . In this implementation the same propagator was used as in the original implementation:

$$P(\Delta z) = e^{-i\text{sign}(k_z)k\Delta z}. \quad (3.16)$$

This propagator differs from the propagator of the in-situ plugin by not containing the transverse wavevector components (eq. (2.23)). The propagated fields are then transformed via an inverse Fourier transform back into position space.

Since a single simulation snapshot was taken, one can't perform a time integration in eq. (2.10), but one needs to refactor the integration with $\Delta t = c\Delta z$ and sum the Poynting vectors along the probe laser propagation axis of the matrix::

$$\mathcal{E}(x, y, z_i) \propto \sum \vec{S}(x, y, z_i; t_s) \vec{e}_z$$

Comparison of in-situ plugin and post-processing implementation

Both the in-situ and the post-processing implementations perform equivalent operations in Fourier space. Thus, one can also use the post-processing implementation to study the influences of the different Fourier space parameters, like the NA or the frequency filter, without having to compile and run a full particle-in-cell simulation each time, one changes one of these parameters, as one would have to do with the in-situ plugin.

A big difference between the in-situ plugin and post-processing implementation is the approach for obtaining the probe laser. The post-processing implementation performs a 3D spatial Fourier transform of the probe laser with a spatial integration to obtain the final shadowgram. The in-situ plugin performs a frequency domain Fourier transform and

3.3. Reference implementation of a post-processing tool

2D spatial Fourier transforms with a final time integration to obtain the shadowgram. Hence, the in-situ approach is closer to the actual image creation process of a CCD in an experiment by actually integrating the probe laser over time.

Furthermore, the in-situ plugin does not need as much space in the simulation box for extracting the probe laser as the post-processing plugin. This leads to smaller simulation boxes in probe laser propagation direction.

One also needs to store field data for the post-processing implementation on a storage system, before it can be loaded and analyzed with the script. The Fourier transformations for the analysis of the relatively small simulation ($432 \times 2560 \times 912$ cells) in section 5.2 already required ~ 128 GB of memory. Job allocations on HPC systems for this amount of memory might still be feasible, but it is definitely not scalable. The in-situ plugin on the other hand allows running larger simulations, by directly using the memory that is available on CPU side and not used otherwise for the PIConGPU simulations.

4. Analyzing post-processing shadowgrams

4.1. Analyzing an LWFA with post-processing shadowgraphy

This chapter will analyze shadowgrams with the post-processing shadowgraphy implementation from section 3.3 for a PIConGPU LWFA simulation. The analyzed simulation is based on the LWFA simulation from [31] because it creates regularly oscillating and distinct plasma structures, which in turn will result into shadowgrams, that are simple to understand and verify. This LWFA setup also creates long-term stable oscillations with a self-injection later on, which will allow to study different pump-probe delays in section 6.2.

The drive laser has the normalized intensity $a_0 = 1.0886$ with a wavelength of 810 nm. The laser is a 3D Gaussian with a pulse length of $\tau_{FWHM} = 36$ fs and the spot size at the FWHM $18.84 \mu\text{m}$ (E^2). It travels along the y -axis with a focus at $y = 300 \mu\text{m}$. The drive laser has a linear polarization along the z -axis.

The probe laser is also a bandwidth limited 3D Gaussian laser. Its intensity is $a_0 = 0.0188$ with a wavelength $\lambda = 750$ nm and duration $\tau_{FWHM} = 12$ fs (E^2). The laser is focused in the center of the plasma wakes, $y = 900 \mu\text{m}$ to a spotsize $235 \mu\text{m}$ (FWHM). It is linearly polarized along the y -axis.

The electron density follows a super Gaussian density profile $n_e(y) = n_0 \exp\{-(y-y_0)^4/w_p^4\}$ with the base density $n_0 = 1.7 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-3}$, $y_0 = 1.17$ mm and $w_p = 1.198$ mm as shown in fig. 4.1.

The grid of the simulation box resolves the wavelengths of the probe and plasma laser 10 times in their respective propagation directions: $\Delta x = 0.15 \mu\text{m}$, $\Delta y = 0.081 \mu\text{m}$ and

Figure 4.1.: Density distribution of this simulation with the drive laser focus position.

4. Analyzing post-processing shadowgrams

Figure 4.2.: Electron density when the probe laser is in the center of the plasma wakes, meaning the center of the simulation box on the z -axis. This is the corresponding electron density for the following shadowgrams. The density is normalized to its mean density ($1.68 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-3}$).

$\Delta z = 0.075 \mu\text{m}$. The time resolution $\Delta t = 0.1381 \text{ fs}$ arises from the CFL (Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy) condition of the used sixth order AOFDTD (arbitrary order FDTD) solver of PIconGPU [55]

$$\Delta t = \frac{0.995}{1.241667 \cdot c \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{1}{\Delta y^2} + \frac{1}{\Delta z^2}}}. \quad (4.1)$$

The longitudinal size of the simulation in drive laser propagation direction y was chosen to possibly contain a large amount of visible plasma cavities in the synthetic shadowgram, similar to experimental shadowgrams. In probe laser propagation direction z , the simulation was chosen to be large enough to fully extract a probe laser with the post-processing tool out of a 3D volume, that does not contain the electric fields from the cavities themselves. The size in x direction was chosen to be the same size as in z direction. This leads to $432 \times 2560 \times 912$ cells and thus to a simulation box size of $64.8 \mu\text{m} \times 207.36 \mu\text{m} \times 68.4 \mu\text{m}$.

One can see that the probe laser is larger than the simulation box, which will lead to some numerical artifacts at the transverse spatial boundaries caused by the PML (perfectly matched layer) simulation box boundaries. However, a position space window function is applied to try to suppress these artifacts. A large probe laser is required, so that the resulting images show all the trailing cavities from the laser wakefield accelerator.

A slice through the plasma density in the (y, x) -plane at $t = 3.11 \text{ ps}$ is shown in fig. 4.2, which is the time where the probe laser maximum overlaps with the center of the plasma density oscillation. Note that the real simulation box size is actually larger than the picture. The simulation requires more space in drive laser propagation direction since the moving window is stopped to prevent some numerical artifacts as soon as the probe laser enters the simulation and the probe laser must propagate through the plasma structures before these exit the stopped simulation box in y -direction.

In the plasma density one can see that the first cavity and the 2 following cavities are completely evacuated and charge starts accumulating at the tail of the first cavity. As expected, the plasma is oscillating with the size of the cavities being the plasma wavelength $\lambda_p \cong 8 \mu\text{m}$.

The fields of the probe laser are extracted $20 \mu\text{m}$ behind the cavity center limiting the simulation output volume on the z -axis to the highlighted volume in fig. 4.3 and 3D Fourier transformed into (k_x, k_y, k_z) -space. Only every second cell was used to compute

4.1. Analyzing an LWFA with post-processing shadowgraphy

Figure 4.3.: Sketch of object plane positions on the z -axis (probe laser propagation direction). The size of the cavity is the theoretical expectation of the plasma cavity size depending on the plasma frequency and is added for visualization purposes. The normalized probe laser envelope is drawn at the extraction position, that is the position of the probe laser at the time of the openPMD output for the post-processing script. The script then computes a 3D Fourier transform of the indicated volume, to propagate the laser onto each of the 3 object planes, then transform it back to position space and finally calculates the shadowgrams. Within the highlighted PML (Perfectly Matched Layer) boundaries the fields are artificially absorbed by PICongGPU, resulting in numerical artifacts. This needs to be considered when extracting the probe laser, meaning electric and magnetic fields, from the simulation box.

the shadowgrams for this chapter to save compute time. Since the resolved cell resolution is large enough, the probe and drive laser wavelengths are still contained within the 3D Fourier domain, as will be visible in section 4.2.

In Fourier space the masks are applied with a numerical aperture $NA = D/2f = 0.26$ and a band-pass filter with $\lambda_p \pm \delta\lambda$ with $\delta\lambda = 50 \text{ nm}$. There are also some additional window function parameters, that will be discussed in the following sections. The probe laser is then vacuum-propagated to the object plane of the lens system at $-10 \mu\text{m}$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$ as shown in fig. 4.3 and a third shadowgram was created with no propagation. Afterwards the E and B fields are transformed back into position space, multiplied to obtain the Poynting vector and this vector is integrated along the longitudinal axis to obtain the final shadowgrams.

The three resulting shadowgrams can be seen in fig. 4.4. Changing the object plane position clearly leads to different shadowgrams. For each position, the signature of the leading cavity in the LWFA changes drastically. The bright area on the left-hand side of the shadowgram at $y \sim 800 \mu\text{m}$, that appears for all positions of the object planes, likely arises from numerical artifacts that are caused by the simulation box being too small for the probe laser. This can be seen later in section 6.3.

With the object plane being far from the wake structures $\Delta z = 10 \mu\text{m}$, one can see a relatively dark, elongated leading cavity and also an elongated second cavity. The further trailing cavities are also visible with periodic dark spots. The electromagnetic waves of the probe laser are strongly refracted by the density gradients of the plasma wake structures. Furthermore, one can see a halo-like diffraction structure around the plasma cavities. When the probe laser is not propagated with the post processing script and the object plane is directly in the center of the extraction volume of the probe laser $\Delta z = 0 \mu\text{m}$, the halo

4. Analyzing post-processing shadowgrams

Figure 4.4.: Post processing shadowgrams. Different object planes of the lens system show different features in the shadowgrams. Several masks and window functions were used to calculate these shadowgrams, which will be discussed in the further section.

Figure 4.5.: Line-out plots through the transverse center of all 3 shadowgrams from fig. 4.4 and the according electron density through the transverse center of the plot. All line-outs are normalized and then given an offset for better comparison. The smoothed density was created by averaging the density values over 10 close cells to suppress the numerical noise.

structures start to disappear and the dark spots at the plasma cavities become smaller. Additionally, more substructures start to develop inside the first, leading cavity of the LWFA. After changing the object plane to be closer to the plasma structures $\Delta z = -10 \mu\text{m}$, the dark spots within the trailing cavities wash out and the previously more triangle-shaped structures that are open to the left-hand side, are now c-shaped structures that are open to the right hand side. The leading cavity does not look elongated anymore and mostly consists of its substructures and the diffraction patterns around the cavities disappear.

The oscillation periods of the shadowgram are shown more clearly in a line-out plot through the center of the cavities in fig. 4.5. The probe laser is strongly refracted at the position of the plasma cavities because of the high density gradients, resulting in local minima at these positions. One can also see that the general plasma density structure seems to be smeared out in the shadowgram, which comes from the fact that the probe laser needs $t \sim 8 \mu\text{m}/c$ to propagate through the structures while the plasma structures are also propagating with the speed of light in an orthogonal direction. The $\lambda = 8 \mu\text{m}$ oscillations can easily be observed in the trailing cavities, agreeing with the cavity diameters. Interestingly this does not perfectly match the transverse size of the first cavities, becoming even larger offsets the closer the plasma structures to the object plane is. The contrast, that is the difference between the local minima and maxima in the energy density of the shadowgrams, actually becomes worse the closer the object plane is to the plasma structure. One cause for the reduction in contrast can be the disappearance of the dark spots, leading to not so distinct minima inside the plot. On the other hand, the diffraction pattern reduces closer to the plasma structures as expected, and the image becomes sharper.

In this line-out plot it is visible that the actual size of the first cavity is difficult to determine by looking at the shadowgram. Due to the high charge at the rear of the cavity, the drive laser in the front and the strong electric and magnetic fields inside the cavity, the probe laser is significantly refracted. However, it is also difficult to determine the length of the first cavity from the electron density itself due to the strong modulation of the drive laser.

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In this simulation one could try to measure the length of the leading cavity by looking at the shadowgram that is created further from the plasma structure $\Delta z = 10 \mu\text{m}$, which has a visible local minimum at the position of the plasma cavity. For $\Delta z = 0 \mu\text{m}$, there are 2 local minima at the beginning and end of the leading cavity due to the bright spot in its center. When the object plane, that is the focus of the lens system, is put closer to the plasma structures, all the plasma structures appear to have an offset, but the size of the leading cavity would be measurable. However, it requires further investigation to fully understand the relation between the shadowgraphic image and the plasma density itself.

Concluding, this line-out plot shows that shadowgrams of LWFAs are a possible tool to determine the density of the plasma by measuring the trailing cavities and exploiting the definition of the plasma wavelength. Furthermore, the relation between the size of the first cavity in the shadowgraphic image and the real size in the plasma density is not straight forward, as one can see by the general complex shape of the first cavity in fig. 4.4 or its line-out plots. Thus, one can use synthetic shadowgrams to develop a method to better relate the cavity size of experimental shadowgrams to the plasma density.

4.2. Window functions

In the previous section different kinds of masks were already applied in the post-processing tool, equivalent to the ones mentioned for the in-situ shadowgraphy plugin in section 3.2. This and the next 2 sections discuss the impact of different masks that are necessary to obtain sharp, high contrast shadowgrams like fig. 4.4, with few artifacts, for direct comparison with experimental shadowgrams.

To demonstrate the necessity of these masks in both position and Fourier space, one can look the top plot of fig. 4.6. The top image is obtained by just propagating the electric and magnetic fields from the simulation box onto the object plane, without including any kind of masks or window functions in neither position nor Fourier space. This "raw" shadowgram includes many artifacts in comparison to experimental shadowgrams.

Side-scattered light from the drive laser of the LWFA is clearly visible in the shadowgram, completely covering the first cavity in the image. There are also whirls on the left hand side of the shadowgram, which are numerical artifacts and originate from the large longitudinal size of the simulation and the stopped moving window. Since there were no periodic particle boundaries enabled in this PIconGPU simulation, the particle distribution stops at the boundaries of the simulation box. Thus, electrons tend to either be pushed out of the simulation box or pulled into the plasma structures, but no new electrons enter the simulation box transversely. Due to the larger longitudinal size of the simulation, this statistical process becomes significant and creates noticeable plasma density structures on the rear side of the simulation box close to the borders. These non-homogeneous plasma density structures create electric fields themselves, which are recorded by the shadowgraphy implementations that are based on extracting fields from the simulation box. One last artifact that is visible in the top figure of fig. 4.6 are the ringing effects, parallel to the simulation box boundaries.

Figure 4.6.: Post processing shadowgrams with different position space window function plateau sizes, relative to the general size of the simulation box. The units are normalized over all shadowgrams within this figure. The upper shadowgram shows a raw shadowgram that is calculated by propagating the electric and magnetic fields to the image plane of the 4f-correlator without applying any other masks or window functions.

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Figure 4.7.: Post processing Fourier space images of the absolute electric field for different position space window function plateau sizes, relative to the general size of the simulation box. The upper pictures show a transverse slice of the electric fields through the probe laser. The lower pictures show the (k_y, k_z) -plane which contains the probe laser that propagates in z direction and the drive laser that propagates in y direction. The corresponding shadowgrams are in fig. 4.6.

This section focuses on removing the latter mentioned ringing effects, since this technique will be used throughout the following sections. Ringing effects originate from performing a DFT, which can only sample a finite, discretized Fourier domain, on functions with hard cut-offs. This is the case for our numerical, spatially limited simulation box and does not appear like this in experimental shadowgrams. To suppress these ringing effects, a window function equivalent to the Tukey window function is introduced:

$$\mathcal{M}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \cos \left(\pi \frac{x-x_0}{x_1-x_0} \right) \right), & x_0 < x \leq x_1 \\ 1, & x_1 < x \leq x_2 \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \cos \left(\pi \frac{x-x_2}{x_3-x_2} \right) \right), & x_2 < x \leq x_3 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

It has sinusoidal slopes leading to constant plateau [56]. The function is visualized for arbitrary coordinates in fig. 4.8. This function is multiplied onto the electric and magnetic fields right after loading them from the data dump, before they are transformed into (k_x, k_y, k_z) -domain. The effect of the window functions are clearly visible in fig. 4.6. For smaller window function plateaus, the high contrast ringing effects disappear from the shadowgram. Additionally, the artifacts, that are caused by the moving window at the simulation box boundaries, also are nearly completely removed, when the moving window plateau is equal to 60 % of the simulation box sizes. However, those smaller window function plateaus also remove the outer parts of the shadowgram, since the electric and magnetic fields basically are set to zero. Therefore, in order to still acquire large shadowgrams that include the complete image of the plasma wake structures, the size of the plateau is set to 80 % for all other shadowgrams in this chapter (chapter 4), which already removes a

Figure 4.8.: The applied window function for generalized coordinates eq. (4.2).

significant amount of the high contrast ringing effects in the image. Furthermore, all other shadowgrams are zoomed in onto the plateau, to hide the part of the image, which does not contain actual information due to the window function.

To further understand the shadowgrams and the effect of the window functions, see the Fourier space slices fig. 4.7 of the simulation with the different window functions. Both the drive and the probe laser are visible in those slices. The drive laser is pointing in the y direction, the probe laser into the z direction. Note that one can see both negative and positive k -components, since this is a 3D Fourier transform of the real electric and magnetic fields from the simulation. Both lasers have the expected length of their k -vectors from the wavelengths $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ with $k_{pr} = 0.838 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and $k_{dr} = 0.776 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^{-1}$. Without the window function, both fields have strong artifacts in the directions parallel to their propagation and polarization directions. These artifacts are suppressed by the window functions for the probe laser. The drive laser still has strong, vertical artifacts in the Fourier plot, but this will be removed by the numerical aperture and band-pass filter in the next two sections.

Interestingly, one can also see, that some electric field components point diagonally into (k_y, k_z) -direction, which appears to have a larger frequency, that is the distance to the origin, than either of the probe and drive lasers. In the (k_y, k_x) -plane this component looks like a half-ellipsoid around the probe laser. One possible origin of this feature is the general asymmetric spatial distribution of the simulation output that is chosen for the 3D Fourier transforms (fig. 4.3). One could try to perform the 3D Fourier transform onto a symmetrical post-processing box from $z = -27 \mu\text{m}$ to $27 \mu\text{m}$ to see if this feature then persists. However, this would require reducing the simulation box resolution due to the memory limited post-processing approach. Otherwise, one could manually remove these electric field components in Fourier space and transform the field back to position space to see where this feature spatially originates. Ultimately this feature does not actually matter for shadowgraphy calculations. Its electric field components are 3 orders of magnitude smaller than the probe laser itself and additionally it can be suppressed by the numerical aperture and frequency filter introduced in the next sections (section 4.3 and section 4.4)

4. Analyzing post-processing shadowgrams

Figure 4.9.: Post processing Fourier space image of the absolute electric field for different numerical apertures. The resulting shadowgrams are in fig. 4.10.

4.3. Numerical aperture

Removal of the side scattered light contribution to shadowgrams by a numerical aperture is explained in this section. In experiments the numerical aperture is equivalent to the acceptance angle of the used imaging system $NA = D/2f$, in the synthetic shadowgraphy tools it is implemented as a cone shaped mask in Fourier space that mimics the experimental function of the numerical aperture.

The electric field in Fourier space, see fig. 4.9, visualizes the impact of the numerical aperture. Due to the NA, only the electric field contributions lying within a cone pointing in the probe laser propagation direction, are transformed back into position space for the final integration. For larger NAs the cone has a larger opening angle, while for smaller NAs the cone has a smaller opening angle and only contributions closer to the probe's propagation axis are used in the calculation. The numerical aperture also removes most of the low-frequency components of the electric fields, which are likely quasi-static electric fields caused by the electrons of the plasma.

The effect of the numerical aperture becomes clearly visible in the resulting shadowgrams fig. 4.10. Applying any NA already removes the drive laser and moving window artifacts, that were visible in the shadowgrams earlier (fig. 4.6). One can also see, that smaller NAs result in blurry images with not as sharp features in the shadowgram, meaning that the resolution is worse for shadowgrams made with larger NAs. But additionally to the higher contrast of the larger apertures, the larger apertures also include more effects that are transverse to the plasma structures, which are caused by either strongly refracted light or just by the quasi static electric fields from the plasma structures themselves. One can also see the vertical ringing effects, that originate from the hard cut-offs from the electric and magnetic fields in Fourier space. This ringing has a higher spatial frequency for $NA = 0.26$

Figure 4.10.: Post processing shadowgrams with different numerical apertures. Additionally to the NA only the position space window functions are applied.

4. Analyzing post-processing shadowgrams

Figure 4.11.: Post processing Fourier space image of the absolute electric field for different NA window function parameters. The parameter corresponds to the constant width of a transverse offset in which a sinusoidal window function is applied. This offset is normalized to the mean k length that is expected from the probe laser's wavelength. The NA is set to 0.26. The resulting shadowgrams are in fig. 4.12.

than for $NA = 0.16$, but it seems to disappear for the larger aperture 0.36. From now on the $NA = 0.26$ is chosen for further computations.

To suppress the ringing here, I have also implemented a window function analogous to eq. (4.2) for the numerical aperture. The width of the slopes of these window functions are determined by a factor multiplied with the absolute k -vector of the probe laser, so that both the large and small frequency components of the electric fields are affected by the same amount of window function. In Fourier space this results in the masks becoming tapered cylinders (fig. 4.11).

The window function results as expected in smoother shadowgrams (fig. 4.12) for larger slopes, similar to the regular effect of the numerical aperture. However, if the window function slopes become too large, side scattered light in the simulation is introduced into the shadowgrams. This is noticeable, where the moving window artifacts are introduced back into the rear end of the shadowgram for the window function factor 0.3, which are visible in the origin in Fourier space. This numerical aperture window function parameter is set to 0.1 for further computations.

Note, that the constant off-set from the numerical aperture window function changes the physical meaning of the numerical aperture by allowing more side-scattered light in the final computation, especially for lower frequencies. For the shadowgrams in chapter 5 and in chapter 6 a frequency filter was applied in addition to the numerical aperture, which will remove the low frequency components. Thus, this is a minor deviation, which does not have a significant influence on the resulting shadowgram.

Figure 4.12.: Post processing shadowgrams with different NA window function slope sizes. The NA is set to 0.26.

4. Analyzing post-processing shadowgrams

Figure 4.13.: Post processing Fourier space of the absolute electric field for different bandwidths for the frequency filter. The resulting shadowgrams are in fig. 4.14.

4.4. Frequency filter

A CCD camera in experiments is only sensitive in a certain wavelength range. Often also a band-pass filter is used to discriminate the probe laser from the drive laser, if they have different wavelengths. This section studies the effects of a band-pass filter to further separate the probe laser from different electric fields for the synthetic shadowgrams. The boundaries of the band-pass filter are $k_{min} < k < k_{max}$ with $k_{min} = 2\pi/(\lambda_p + \delta\lambda)$ and $k_{max} = 2\pi/(\lambda_p - \delta\lambda)$.

In Fourier space (fig. 4.13), the band-pass filter creates a hollow sphere of the given width. This sphere always includes the probe laser, and for increasing bandwidths it includes more components of the drive laser. This is due to the fact that the drive laser and probe laser lie close together with $\lambda_{dr} = 810$ nm and $\lambda_{pr} = 750$ nm and their spectral width is determined by the time-bandwidth product due to their short duration. When decreasing the bandwidth of the frequency filter, one needs to consider the time-bandwidth product as well, since the resulting position space pulse length larger than the original read out volume, meaning that information of the probe pulse is discarded. Additionally, the frequency filter is useful to remove the low-frequency components of the electric fields.

The effects in the resulting shadowgram are similar to the effects of the NA from the previous chapter fig. 4.14. For larger bandwidths, side scattered light from the drive laser is included in the images, which will be removed by using smaller bandwidths. Furthermore, the frequency filter also removes the moving window artifacts from fig. 4.6. Interestingly one can see a longitudinal wave-like pattern with a periodicity $\lambda < 1$ μ m in the leading cavities, which has its strongest intensity for $\delta\lambda = 50$ nm, but it is also visible for the smaller bandwidth. Since it is most dominantly visible in the first cavity, it is assumed

Figure 4.14.: Post-processing shadowgrams with different bandwidths. Only the position space window functions are applied additionally to the band-pass filter. Three separate color bars are chosen in this plot, because the actual energy density \mathcal{E} for the different shadowgrams differs a lot due to the inclusion of the drive laser and the total spectral width of the probe pulse.

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Figure 4.15.: Post-processing Fourier space images of different frequency filter window functions for a bandwidth of $\delta\lambda = 50$ nm. The parameter corresponds to the length of a sinusoidal slope that is normalized to the plateau bandwidth.

that these are side-scattered light artifacts from the drive laser and they disappear for the larger band-pass filter due to the normalized color bars.

A window function similar to the window function from the previous chapter has been implemented for the frequency filter, see fig. 4.15. Here, a window function parameter of 1 is equivalent to a slope in eq. (4.2) being exactly the size of the plateau $2\delta k = 2(k_{max} - k_{min})$. A larger window function parameter means larger slopes for the spherical mask in both directions. This window function is supposed to remove ringing effects longitudinally to the probe laser, that originates from the hard cut-offs of the band-pass filter. But since the shadowgraphy implementation integrates along the axis z axis to compute the final image, this window function does not lead to any visible effects in the resulting shadowgrams shown in fig. 4.16. Thus, it would be more beneficial to quantitatively optimize the window function implementation. Since the post-processing plugin was designed to qualitatively generate synthetic shadowgrams, it is not further investigated at the moment. The applied bandwidths in the band-pass filter are generally quite small. Thus, it might be useful to look into other window functions like Hann or Blackman-Harris window functions, which are more optimized for short signals.

In conclusion, this chapter has shown the implementation of several shadowgraphy parameters, that mimic the experimental setup and remove numerical artifacts. The experimental parameters, the numerical aperture and the frequency filter, are both useful to enhance the shadowgrams and reproduce experimental shadowgrams synthetically. If both of them are combined together, side scattered light from the drive laser and low-frequency components from the quasi-static electric fields from the plasma of the PIConGPU simulation can be removed from the shadowgram. Also, several window functions were introduced, that remove the ringing effects.

Figure 4.16.: Post processing shadowgrams with different bandwidth window-functions. Additionally to the band-pass filter with $\delta\lambda = 50\text{ nm}$ only the position space window functions are applied. These shadowgrams correspond to the Fourier space images fig. 4.15.

5. Validation of the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

5.1. Quantitative analysis using a Gaussian laser pulse

The aim of this section is to quantitatively validate the electric and magnetic field extraction and the frequency domain Fourier transform of the in-situ shadowgraphy plugin for PIConGPU. This will be done by writing the interim result of the frequency domain Fourier transform in (x, y, ω) -domain to a file, before it is transformed into (k_x, k_y, ω) -domain and the masks and propagation are applied. The plugin output will be validated by using a Gaussian shaped laser in a vacuum simulation, since it can easily be validated with its theoretical envelope. Since all components of the electric and magnetic fields are handled identically as scalar waves, this section focuses on the polarization component of the electric field of the laser.

The Gaussian shaped laser is implemented via the "fieldbackground" method in PIConGPU [57], linearly polarized in x direction and propagates in z direction with the wavelength $\lambda = 800$ nm, which is equal to the angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi/\lambda = 2.35 \times 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The FWHM (full width at half maximum) duration of the intensity (E^2) envelope of the laser is $\tau_{FWHM} = 10.36$ fs, or as standard deviation $\sigma_\tau = 1/(2\sqrt{2 \ln 2})\tau_{FWHM} \approx 4.4$ fs. Transversely the laser's waist is $w_0 = 10 \mu\text{m}$ (distance from the transverse center over which E^2 decreases to its $1/e^2$ -Jth part), which is equivalent to $\sigma = w_0/2 = 5 \mu\text{m}$ or FWHM = $11.77 \mu\text{m}$. The laser is set to be in focus in the center of the simulation box at the time $\mu_t = 50$ fs. The laser is also initialized with $a_0 = 1$, which is equal to a maximum electric field amplitude $E_0 = 4.013 \times 10^{12} \text{ Vm}^{-1}$ in focus. The cells of the simulation box are cubic with a width $\Delta x = \lambda/10 = 8 \times 10^{-8}$ m, leading to the timestep $\Delta t = 0.995\Delta x/(c\sqrt{3}) = 1.5329 \times 10^{-16}$ s from the CFL condition with the default Yee field solver. The simulation box was set to $512 \times 512 \times 64$ cells. The plugin now records the laser over 950 timesteps, to ensure a high resolution image in ω -space.

Due to the time-bandwidth product, the expected spectral width of the probe laser ω_{FWHM} can be calculated with the time bandwidth product $\omega_{FWHM} = 0.441 \cdot 2\pi/\tau_{FWHM} = 0.268 \times 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [58]. This influences the plugin parameters insofar that per default a bandpass-filter is applied in ω -domain to save memory ($n_\omega \leq n_t$). Thus, the simulation is run twice. First, the Fourier transform is calculated for $6\omega_{FWHM}$. Second, the Fourier transform is calculated for $12\omega_{FWHM}$ to demonstrate the difference of a larger frequency domain. Unlike otherwise stated, the presented results are from the $6\omega_{FWHM}$ simulation.

The validation of the simulation output happens in three steps. First, this section analyses the interim output of the simulation directly in frequency-domain. Second, the interim

5. Validation of the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

Figure 5.1.: Line-out plot of the interim simulation output in (x,y,ω) -space at the spatial center. The left plot shows the real values for the full ω space, the right plot shows the absolute values only for $\omega > 0$. The dotted line features the expected central probe laser frequency.

Figure 5.2.: Left: The reconstructed laser profile and the theoretical expectation on a linear and on a logarithmic scale. The linear scale is plotted to better visualize the Gaussian shape, but the logarithmic scale helps to show the introduced deviations for lower field strengths. Right: The relative error of the reconstructed laser profile with the simulation result of the reconstruction from the left as a dashed line.

output is transformed with a separate tool into time-domain for comparison to the expected envelop. Third, the resulting image will be analyzed briefly.

For the first step of the validation, fig. 5.1 shows the interim plugin output after the last step of the frequency domain Fourier transform in (x,y,ω) -domain as a line-out through the spatial center. In the right plot one can clearly see that the central frequency ω is at the expected position $\omega = (2.35 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The uncertainty corresponds to the plugin's frequency step given by the plugin duration. The width at the FWHM of this spectrum is measured directly in the $E(\omega)$ array. With a division by $\sqrt{2}$ to adjust for the difference in electric field and intensity, this leads to $\omega_{\text{FWHM}} = (0.27 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which agrees with the input values.

The second step of the validation compares the interim output to the expected electric field in a more straightforward approach by Fourier transforming it back from the ω to time domain. The envelop of the time-domain E -field can then be compared to a Gaussian function $\propto \exp\{-1/2((t - \mu)/(\pi\sigma))^2\}$ with the values from the simulation input. This envelop is calculated by padding the $E(\omega)$ array to the original size n_ω . Since the original PICongPU electric field is a real field and the Fourier transform of a real function is

5.1. Quantitative analysis using a Gaussian laser pulse

Figure 5.3.: The left picture shows the reconstructed laser profile with a readjusted mean value of the theoretical expectation and its error. The right side shows the reconstructed laser profile from the simulation with the larger frequency domain.

symmetric, only the $\omega > 0$ values are filled with the plugin output in order to obtain the envelope in time domain. This field subsequently is transformed via an inverse Fourier transformation from the numpy library back to time domain [59]. It is normalized by the value n_ω , multiplied with the factor 2 due to the symmetry operation, and the absolute value is taken.

Figure 5.2 shows on the left the reconstructed electric field envelop and the expectation value from the simulation input on a linear and a logarithmic scale. On the right, the relative error Δ between both functions is shown,

$$\Delta = 2 \frac{f(x) - g(x)}{|f(x)| + |g(x)|}. \quad (5.1)$$

The relative error can now be used to validate the field extraction and the time domain Fourier transform of the in-situ plugin. It shows, that the maximum, that is the maximum of the electric field amplitude, and the width of the Gaussian distribution, that is the laser duration, agree with each other. The relative error of the maximum from the envelop to the maximum of the expectation value is 0.004 %.

It is interesting to note, that the mean value, that is the time delay of the probe pulse, of the simulation output seems to be off, which is indicated by the linear slope in the relative error plot. It was found by manually readjusting the Gaussian function, that it is roughly $\sim 1.76\Delta t$ too large in the simulation output. Figure 5.3 shows the relative error of the simulation output and the readjusted Gaussian function compared to each other, which removes the linear slope in the relative error and further shows that the maximum and the width of the Gaussian functions agree with each other. However, since the plugin ultimately performs a time integration, this systematic error introduced by the offset of the mean value, can be neglected.

The small value tails of the reconstructed Gaussian function do not reach the small values like an optimal Gaussian function, which is due to the finite size of the DFT and also band-pass filter of the simulation output. The introduced uncertainty from that is $\propto 10^{-6}$ to 10^{-7} relative to the maximum intensity, which is negligible in the final shadowgram. One can also see 2 minima in the relative error. These errors are caused by the hard cut-off in the

5. Validation of the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

Figure 5.4.: The "shadowgram" of the Gaussian laser pulse with a line-out through the center of the 2d shadowgram. The shadowgram is computed with the shadowgraphy plugin exactly like the previous and following shadowgrams of LWFA. The underlying simulation box only contains a vacuum, therefore one can not see an actual "shadow" of a density gradient distribution in this image, but it reproduces as expected the transverse Gaussian profile of the laser.

frequency domain before the field is transformed back into time domain, which causes ringing effects.

The right figure in fig. 5.3 is created with the earlier mentioned larger frequency domain $12\omega_{FWHM}$ without the readjusted theoretical Gaussian distribution. Due to the larger ω -domain, the tails of the Gaussian function can be reconstructed better by one order of magnitude. Although this is not shown, this plot will behave like the plot on the left handed side, if it is plotted with the readjusted Gaussian function with the same $\mu \rightarrow \mu + 1.76\Delta t$, meaning that the linear slope in the relative error disappears.

As third part of the validation, the final image is shown in fig. 5.4. The numerically calculated width of the Gaussian laser in the shadowgram at half the maximum intensity is $FWHM = (11.84 \pm 0.08) \mu m$, where the uncertainty is the cell resolution. This matches the expected width of the laser.

5.2. Qualitative comparison to post-processing reference implementation

Here I compare the output of the PIconGPU in-situ plugin qualitatively with the output of the reference post-processing implementation from section 3.3. Since the python post-processing implementation performs a 3D spatial Fourier transformation, while the in-situ plugin performs a time domain Fourier transformation, some differences between both

5.2. Qualitative comparison to post-processing reference implementation

Figure 5.5.: Electron density, normalized to the mean value of the density. Same as fig. 4.2, printed for convenience.

implementations are expected. The shadowgram results from the plugin implementation are expected to produce results, that are closer to experimental shadowgrams, because they perform a direct time integration like an actual CCD. However, this does not hamper the qualitative comparison of both implementations. One can still look at different features that appear in the shadowgrams and how they change with respect to various object plane positions, that is focus positions of the lens system.

The LWFA simulation from chapter 4 is used again as a benchmark, where the probe laser is focused at 900 μm . The related electron density, when the probe laser is in the center of the wake structure is shown in fig. 5.5. The drive laser ($a_0 = 1.0886$) undergoes self-focusing, whereby it evacuates the first cavity and it creates periodic trailing cavities.

The shadowgraphy setup is shown in fig. 5.6. The 3D spatially Fourier transformed box for the post-processing script, that contains the probe laser, is highlighted with the purple lines. Unlike the previous chapter, where every second spatial cell was used to calculate the shadowgrams with the post-processing script, this section will use higher resolution post-processing shadowgrams by including each spatial cell to make the images more comparable to the plugin. The probe laser is then propagated to each of the 5 indicated object planes in fig. 5.6. For the plugin, the probe laser is time-recorded directly at the $\Delta z = 0 \mu\text{m}$ object plane and then also propagated to each of the 5 object planes.

Figure 5.7 and fig. 5.8 show the results from the plugin and the post-processing script respectively. The trailing cavities look very similar with both shadowgraphy implementations. For propagation distances further from the plasma structures, there are dark spots in the center of the trailing cavities. These dark spots disappear and are replaced by smaller c-shaped features, when propagating closer to the plasma cavities, for both implementations. The only, significant difference in both implementations appears in the leading cavity. For larger propagation distances $\Delta z \geq 0 \mu\text{m}$ both leading cavities look similar, but for negative propagation distances, especially for $\Delta z = -10 \mu\text{m}$, a bright sub-feature appears in the leading cavity of the post-processing implementation. One possible explanation for this difference could be, that the assumed 3D Fourier transformation approach of the post-processing script contains stronger temporal coherence effects for these features, which will average out when the probe laser is propagating within PIconGPU through the integrating plane. This difference could also be caused by the

5. Validation of the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

Figure 5.6.: This figure shows the object planes for the following shadowgrams in relation to the simulation box and the expected plasma cavity size from the plasma density. The probe laser is shown within the box that is used for the post-processing script. For the plugin, the probe laser is recorded and Fourier transformed into the ω -domain directly at the object plane $\Delta z = 0 \mu\text{m}$. The object plane at $\Delta z = 20 \mu\text{m}$ demonstrates, how the virtual propagation with the post-processing script, or the plugin respectively, is important, since it allows one to use smaller, transverse simulation box sizes.

different propagators that are used, since the plugin propagation of the angular spectrum eq. (2.23) includes transverse components of the wave vector, whereas the post-processing propagator ignores the transverse components and only depends on the overall length of the wavevector. Otherwise, both methods for computing shadowgrams also create the same diffracting structures for all object plane positions.

Figure 5.9 shows the line-out plots from fig. 5.7 and fig. 5.8 compared to the plasma density. The line-outs solidify that the plugin and post-processing produce identical images for $\Delta z \geq 0 \mu\text{m}$, where both the shape of the trailing and of the leading cavity agree with each other. For smaller propagation distances $\Delta z < 0$, the contrast of the shadowgrams of both implementations slowly starts to decrease and the images begin to appear blurry, meaning the difference between the local minima and maxima decreases. However, this might just be an effect of the chosen color scale, which includes the darker spots in the trailing cavities for the propagation distances further from the plasma structures and also of the fact that one just looks at a line-out plot through the center of the shadowgram. Section 6.1 will also reveal, that this effect is wavelength dependent.

For the future, the in-situ shadowgram should be compared to experimental shadowgrams to see if the synthetic shadowgrams work as expected and the behavior of the virtual lens system reproduces experimental results.

For now, I conclude a successful validation of the in-situ plugin from the results presented in this chapter and I will use the in-situ plugin in the next chapter to create more shadowgrams. The in-situ plugin accurately performs a frequency domain Fourier transformation on a laser pulse with an introduced error that is caused by simple machine precision (section 5.1). Additionally, the in-situ plugin reproduces the post-processing results for LWFA

5.2. Qualitative comparison to post-processing reference implementation

Figure 5.7.: Plugin shadowgrams for all 5 propagation distances.

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Figure 5.8.: Post processing shadowgrams for all 5 propagation distances.

5.2. Qualitative comparison to post-processing reference implementation

Figure 5.9.: Line-out plots for all 5 propagation distances from the plugin (fig. 5.7) and post-processing shadowgrams (fig. 5.8).

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shadowgrams with different focus positions of the virtual lens system. The minor differences between both implementations are likely caused by either the propagator of the in-situ plugin, that also includes the transverse wave-vector components or the time-integration approach, which is happening equivalently on an experimental CCD. Thus, it is likely, that the in-situ plugin produces shadowgrams, that are closer to experimental shadowgrams, than the post-processing implementation (section 5.2).

6. Studying synthetic shadowgrams obtained with the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

6.1. Impact of different probe laser wavelengths on the shadowgram

This section demonstrates the effects of different probe laser wavelengths on the resulting shadowgrams for different focus positions of the virtual imaging system. To this end, the previous simulation setup from chapter 4 is used again, but the wavelength of the bandwidth limited probe pulse is changed. Otherwise, the probe pulse retains the normalized field strength $a_0 = 0.0188$, the polarization along the y -axis and a Gaussian shape. The probe pulse duration of the intensity (E^2) is $\tau_{FWHM} = 12$ fs and the spotsize $w_0 = 200$ μm . For simplicity and to save run time, the simulation is restarted from a checkpoint, just before the probe pulse enters the simulation box for its focal position at $y = 900$ μm . This means that the simulation grid stays the same, noticeably with the resolution in probe laser propagation direction $\Delta z = 0.075$ μm . The chosen wavelengths of interest are $\lambda_{pr} = 515$ nm, 600 nm, 700 nm, 750 nm, 800 nm and 900 nm. This wavelength was chosen, because ultra-short laser pulses at this wavelength are commercially available and one of these is commonly used as a probe in ion-acceleration experiments at the DRACO Petawatt laser [29, 60].

The shadowgrams are created with the in-situ shadowgraphy plugin directly within PIconGPU with a numerical aperture $NA = D/2f = 0.26$ and a constant window function offset of $0.05 \omega_{pr}$, as in section 4.3. The total plateau size of the band-pass filter is equivalent to 1.5 the spectral width $0.441 \cdot 2\pi/\tau_{FWHM}$ of the probe pulse. The sinusoidal slopes of the spectral window function have a length of half the spectral width. For the slopes of the positional window function a size of 36 cells is chosen in each transverse direction. The probe laser is recorded over 620 timesteps, $\Delta t = 856$ fs, centered around the probe pulse. Each probe laser is propagated -20 and $+20$ μm to the object plane as shown in fig. 6.1, resulting in 2 shadowgrams per wavelength, to study different focus position effects.

The resulting shadowgrams can be seen in fig. 6.2. This section analyzes these shadowgrams in four major steps. First, the general, macroscopic properties of the different shadowgrams are discussed, e.g. the overall energy density and the resolution of the shadowgrams. Second, diffraction effects are shown. Third, spatially smaller details in the the leading cavity will be discussed.

First, the measured energy density decreases with increasing wavelengths, which originates from the dependence of the intensity of the laser on the wavelength $\propto 1/\lambda^2$.

6. Studying synthetic shadowgrams obtained with the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

Figure 6.1.: The position of the plugin integration plane which records the probe laser passing through it. The probe laser is then propagated to the object plane of the lens system at the indicated positions. The cavity size on the z -axis is equivalent to the expected cavity size from the plasma wavelength, the probe laser's longitudinal profile is visualized for scale at an arbitrary position.

The spatial energy distribution in the shadowgrams for $\lambda > 700 \text{ nm}$ increases to the boundary as already previously seen in this thesis. This does not appear for $\lambda \leq 600 \text{ nm}$ and the shape of the probe pulse is visible as naively expected for a Gaussian laser, by having a maximum at the focal position. Because this effect appears in both the post-processing and the in-situ implementation (section 5.2), it is likely, that this is a refraction artifact, that is caused directly by the particle-in-cell algorithm itself from the simulation box being too small for the used probe laser. The large probe laser is however required to evenly illuminate the complete accelerator.

Generally if one decreases the wavelength, one would expect a higher resolution picture. This can be observed in the shadowgrams, where sharper features are visible in the small wavelength images. However, if one decreases the wavelength of the probe laser, one also needs to consider that the refractive index depends on the wavelength $\eta = \sqrt{1 - \omega_p^2 / \omega_{probe}^2}$ (eq. (2.6)) and the difference between different refractive indices becomes smaller. Thus, the overall, relative contrast of the small wavelength images decreases. This is especially visible in the longitudinal center of the plasma wakes, where the relative contrast decreases for shorter wavelengths.

Second, different diffraction patterns are visible in the shadowgrams, which depend on the probe laser wavelength. As expected, these diffraction patterns become less distinct, if the focus position of the lens system is moved into the plasma cavities $\Delta z = -20 \mu\text{m}$.

The diffraction pattern transverse to the leading cavity is visible for both focus positions, but it is more distinct when the object plane is set to $\Delta z = 20 \mu\text{m}$. For smaller wavelengths the periodicity of the pattern becomes smaller, as expected. This pattern is not very visible anymore for the higher wavelengths except for a single diffraction ring around the first cavity.

6.1. Impact of different probe laser wavelengths on the shadowgram

Figure 6.2.: Plugin shadowgrams with different wavelengths (rows) and focus positions (columns). The colorbars are fixed for each wavelength. The ringing and probe laser artifacts, which visible as the bright/dark spots at the edges and corners of the shadowgrams lie outside the colorbars. This was chosen to enable a better contrast within the shadowgram itself.

6. Studying synthetic shadowgrams obtained with the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

Furthermore, there is a diffraction pattern around the trailing cavities at $\Delta z = 20 \mu\text{m}$. When the object plane is put into the center of the plasma cavity $\Delta z = -20 \mu\text{m}$, the trailing cavities become a sharp periodic structure in the shadowgram.

Third, looking at the first cavity in the electron density corresponding to these shadowgrams, fig. 5.5 displays a density modulation that is parallel to the drive laser axis originating from the widest point of the plasma cavity, that is the bow-shock of the wakefield. The bow-shock is non-relativistic and thus visible for the probe laser. Turning back to shadowgrams, a very similar shape is directly visible in the $\lambda = 515 \text{ nm}$ shadowgram if the focus is put inside the first cavity $\Delta z = -20 \mu\text{m}$. This shape diminishes with respect to the diffraction pattern for higher wavelengths until it completely disappears for $\lambda \geq 700 \text{ nm}$.

Furthermore, a bright spot is visible in the leading cavity for small wavelengths. An explanation for this spot might be the relativistic electron cyclotron resonance (RECR) [25], where the probe laser experiences a strong birefringence due to the motion of the plasma electrons close to the drive laser. This RECR depends on the drive laser's normalized vector potential and the probe laser's wavelength in a way that it might occur if we assume self-focusing of the drive laser to an $a_0 \sim 2.5$ for these wavelengths. However, the RECR should appear closer to the head of the leading cavity and not in its center.

In conclusion it was shown, that the choice of the probe laser wavelength has drastic effects on the resulting shadowgrams. Shorter wavelengths lead to shadowgrams with a higher resolution, but due to the probe laser dependence of the plasma refraction index eq. (2.6) the general contrast becomes worse, especially in the trailing cavities. On the other hand, the shape of the first cavity can be seen more clearly in the shorter wavelength shadowgrams. Hence, one might be interested in using shorter wavelength shadowgrams for analyzing the leading cavity of LWFA's and longer wavelengths to analyze the longitudinal size of the trailing cavities. It was also shown, that the position of the focus position has a strong influence on the resulting shadowgrams. Focusing directly onto the cavities allows to see the plasma structures more clearly and less disturbed by diffraction effects. If the focus position is further away from the plasma cavities, the refracted light can give a clearer periodic signal to determine the longitudinal cavity size.

Figure 6.3.: Sketch of the shadowgraphy setup. The probe laser is extracted at the drawn through line and then propagated to the three dotted lines to calculate the shadowgrams. Note that the plasma cavity is drawn with its size as the theoretical, predicted size from the plasma wavelength. The probe laser envelop is included for scale.

6.2. Analyzing different stages of an LWFA by computing shadowgrams with different pump-probe delays

Whereas all previously computed synthetic shadowgrams were computed for the same electron density distributions but with either different parameters of the lens-system for the shadowgraphy setup or different probe pulse parameters, this section focuses on analyzing shadowgrams for another 2 different density distributions. This is achieved by moving the focus of the probe laser from the previously used simulation setup (chapter 4) 300 μ m to the front or the back on the drive laser propagation axis and adjusting the timing accordingly.

The density slices in fig. 6.4, fig. 6.5 and fig. 6.6 show, that the resulting stages of the LWFA are distinct. The first 2 density snapshots show different, pronounced and periodic plasma structures without an injection and between 900 μ m and 1200 μ m electrons are injected into the first cavity and accelerated. In the 1200 μ m-density the leading cavity also appears longitudinally elongated.

The shadowgrams are computed by the in-situ plugin for three different object positions at the three different times in the acceleration process. One object plane is put at the back of the plasma cavities and one in the front of the plasma cavities. The "front" and "back" here are determined by the distances from the extraction plane to the transverse center of the simulation plus and minus half of the plasma wavelength $\lambda_p \simeq 8 \mu$ m as shown in fig. 6.3. These object planes are chosen to mimic the usual local experimental setup of shadowgraphy experiments. The third object plane is put 20 μ m behind the extraction plane to show further, more drastic changes in the resulting shadowgraphy images if the lens-system is off-focus.

6. Studying synthetic shadowgrams obtained with the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

Figure 6.4.: Three computed shadowgrams at different object planes with the corresponding plasma density for the probe laser focus at 600 μm .

6.2. Analyzing different stages of an LWFA by computing shadowgrams with different pump-probe delays

Figure 6.5.: Three computed shadowgrams at different object planes with the corresponding plasma density for the probe laser focus at $900\ \mu\text{m}$.

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This analysis is split into three parts. Since the density and according shadowgrams for the focus at 900 μm were already discussed in detail in the previous sections and chapters, the first and second part are an analysis of the 600 μm and 1200 μm sets of plasma density and corresponding shadowgrams compared to the 900 μm set. Third, line-out plots are presented, which will be used to analyze the longitudinal size of especially the leading cavity.

Firstly, with the probe focus at 600 μm not just the plasma density (fig. 6.4), but also the shadowgrams look similar to the known 900 μm (fig. 6.5). In the plasma density the first 2 cavities are evacuated without an injection, but with the difference to the 900 μm -simulation that the transverse size of the trailing cavities is much smaller and the cavities are not round, but more elliptical. However, especially the shadowgrams, that are focused on the plasma cavities directly, show stronger differences.

The leading cavity of the 600 μm -simulation appears with a weaker, relative contrast as in the 900 μm -simulation. The images with object planes, that are focused on the front and back of the plasma cavities, only vaguely show the outlines for the leading cavity. This could be caused by a smaller local electron density at the rear of the cavity, causing the light to refract less. But one can also see in fig. 6.7, that the front of the first cavity has a shallower density gradient, which also results in a weaker refraction.

Furthermore, the slimmer trailing cavities of the earlier probe delay can also be seen as slimmer cavities in the shadowgrams, if those are focused onto the cavity. Interestingly, if the lens system is focused further away at $\Delta z = 20 \mu\text{m}$, the cavities appear with the same size in both shadowgrams.

It is also visible, that focusing on the back (from the perspective of the imaging system) of the cavity leads to different shadowgrams compared to focusing on the front. The shadowgrams, that are focused on back, look more similar to the actual density distribution of the cavity. However, if the shadowgram is focused onto the front of the cavity, the dark spots appear in the center of the cavities, which in turn increases the contrast of the picture.

Additionally, the general plasma density, transversely further away from the plasma wake in the 600 μm set is still quite homogeneous compared to the density for the 900 μm set and the LWFA did not start driving some wider oscillations within the plasma yet. However, this has no apparent effect on the resulting shadowgram, since these density fluctuations seem to be too small and continuous to refract the probe laser significantly.

Secondly, turning to the 1200 μm -set (fig. 6.6), both a very different electron density distribution and also different resulting shadowgrams compared to the previous probe delays are visible. These shadowgrams demonstrate, that it is important to find a better way to visualize the plasma densities for shadowgraphy, since shadowgraphy is not just a picture of this density-slice, but a longitudinal integration over the whole probe laser propagation axis. The shadowgrams are not mirrored at all on the y -axis, although the plasma density looks symmetric in the (x,y) -plane. If one further investigates the plasma density evolution of the simulation, especially in the (z,y) -plane, the rather continuous injection visible in fig. 6.6 causes unstable hosing-like structures. This hosing-like oscillation leads to some relativistic electrons from the boundaries of the second cavity being pushed away under a 30° angle from the wave structures, which caused an asymmetric plasma density disturbance.

6.2. Analyzing different stages of an LWFA by computing shadowgrams with different pump-probe delays

Figure 6.6.: Three computed shadowgrams at different object planes with the corresponding plasma density for the probe laser focus at $1200 \mu\text{m}$.

6. Studying synthetic shadowgrams obtained with the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

Thus, the probe laser is further refracted in a small, not fully evacuated cavity, that is invisible in the density slice through the center of the z -axis. This asymmetric effect shows, that even rather small density disturbances are captured and visible within shadowgrams and this can also be captured by synthetic shadowgrams calculated with PIConGPU. Notably, this leads to the "front" and "back"-images looking basically identically in the trailing cavities, meaning that although a periodic oscillation is visible, the focus effect is now dominated by this asymmetric effect.

Furthermore, the injected electrons in the first cavity are not visible in the shadowgram, where the leading cavity looks like an enlarged cavity from the previous shadowgrams. This shows that the electrons, which are accelerated over a distance $\Delta y \lesssim 200 \mu\text{m}$ with a plasma frequency $\omega_p = \sqrt{n_e e^2 / m_e \epsilon_0} = 0.23 \times 10^{15} \text{s}^{-1}$ leading with accelerating fields $E_0 = 396.47 \text{GVm}^{-1}$ (eq. (2.3)) to electrons energies of $E \simeq 80 \text{MeV}$. These energies are equivalent to an electron Lorentz factor $\gamma \simeq 155$, making the accelerated electrons transparent to the probe laser due to the relativistic refraction index eq. (2.7).

Third, fig. 6.7 shows the line-out plots for the shadowgrams for the three different probe pulse delays with the according plasma densities. This can be used together with the actual shadowgrams to measure the plasma cavity sizes. For all probe delays the latter cavities show a clear oscillation with the plasma wavelength in both the density and the shadowgram line-outs, although this is as expected more challenging due to the asymmetry in the $1200 \mu\text{m}$ shadowgram.

The longitudinal size of the leading cavity can be measured with the shadowgraphy object plane at the back of the cavity for the $600 \mu\text{m}$ and $900 \mu\text{m}$ simulations. Yet, the local maxima to read this length are interestingly a bit off-set to the left $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$. When the focus is at the front of the cavity, it seems to be more challenging to measure the cavity size, since it appears slightly elongated in the line-out plot. For the off-focus images, the cavity appears to be even more enlarged in these line-out plots, although this might be caused by the diffraction effects around the first cavity. Thus, it is advisable to use the 2D shadowgraphy image additionally to the line-out plot to better interpret the diffraction effects around the leading cavity and find the correct cavity size.

Furthermore, the first cavity is elongated up to $\sim 14 \mu\text{m}$ in the shadowgram for the $1200 \mu\text{m}$ simulation. This elongation is a sign for the drive laser being actually stronger than the initial $a_0 = 1.0886$, but also such a cavity elongation comes from wider drive lasers, whose transverse ponderomotive force has a lengthening effect on the local plasma wavelength [61]. This cavity elongation can also be seen in the 2D shadowgrams, but it is more challenging to identify this cavity elongation in the line-out plot.

In conclusion it is shown, that different pump-probe delays lead to different shadowgrams at different object planes. The synthetic shadowgrams from the in-situ plugin can help identify the features, that one can use in an experiment to determine the actual leading cavity size with experimental shadowgraphy. A lens system with multiple focus positions located around the plasma wakes can help with reconstructing a 3D plasma density out of the shadowgrams. However, off-focus shadowgrams might help to determine the plasma wavelength due to the higher contrast of the strongly refracted light inside the trailing cavities. Additionally, it is shown that asymmetric plasma density effects, like secondary, beam-driven plasma cavities, have a significant effect on the resulting shadowgrams.

6.2. Analyzing different stages of an LWFA by computing shadowgrams with different pump-probe delays

Figure 6.7.: Line-out plots for the shadowgrams from fig. 6.4, fig. 6.5 and fig. 6.6 with the corresponding plasma density.

6. Studying synthetic shadowgrams obtained with the in-situ shadowgraphy diagnostic

Figure 6.8.: Sketch of the shadowgraphy setup. The probe laser is extracted at the 8 dotted lines (as well as one more time at the drawn through line). Then the shadowgrams are calculated both directly at the extraction position or propagated to the drawn through line. Note that the plasma cavity is drawn with its size as the theoretical, predicted size from the plasma wavelength. The probe laser is included for scale.

6.3. Studying the evolution of a single shadowgram from within the plasma wake

The previous sections have shown, that it is challenging to interpret the origin of certain features within shadowgrams, if only the 2D time-integrated images and the corresponding density slice exist. This section will demonstrate, how the in-situ plugin can be used to determine the origin of specific features from a single shadowgram. When the extraction planes of the in-situ plugin are put directly into the observed plasma structures, the generation of specific shadowgraphy features is traced. This unique approach for analyzing a shadowgram is only possible due to the design of the PIConGPU shadowgraphy plugin and would not be possible with the post-processing approach, since the plugin extracts the probe laser at a specific z -coordinate, but the post processing approach requires a 3D volume. Obviously this analyzing approach is also not possible to copy within an experiment, but it allows for much more detailed insight into the evolution of single shadowgrams, which can in turn help with interpreting experimental shadowgrams.

For the LWFA simulation and computations of the shadowgram, the same parameters are used as in section 4.1 with a $\lambda_{pr} = 750$ nm probe laser that is focused at $900 \mu\text{m}$. The 9 used integrating planes are shown in fig. 6.8. Since the probe laser arrives at the different z positions at different times within the simulation, the time where the plugin starts recording has to be adjusted accordingly. After the probe laser was fully transformed into the ω -domain, one shadowgram was computed directly at the extraction position and one shadowgram was computed by vacuum-propagating the probe laser to the ninth extraction position.

The resulting shadowgrams are shown in fig. 6.9. This section will be structured in four

6.3. Studying the evolution of a single shadowgram from within the plasma wake

Figure 6.9.: The evolution of the shadowgram from within the plasma cavities (fig. 6.8), where the first row shows the probe laser just after it entered the simulation box over multiple steps until the last picture shows the final shadowgram. The left-hand side show unpropagated shadowgrams, where the object plane is directly at the extraction position, in the right-hand side the probe laser is vacuum-propagated from the extraction position to the extraction plane of the previous sections z_8 .

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parts. First, it will be discussed, how the shadowgram changes from $z = z_7$ to $z = z_8$. Second, the general impact of the virtual probe laser propagation to $z = z_8$ in the in-situ plugin. Third, the source of the trailing cavity signature in the resulting shadowgram. Fourth, the origin of first cavity signature, especially of the plasma bow-shock.

First, the propagation of the probe laser within PIconGPU from $z = z_7$ to $z = z_8$ should just be a propagation through homogeneous plasma and hence no big difference between the $z = z_8$ and the propagated $z = z_7$ density is expected, except for a constant energy loss due to scattering on the electrons. However, the colors of the shadowgram features between both images seem to invert. For example, the c-shape behind the cavity appears darker than the bright spot in center of the cavity in $z = z_7$, but it appears brighter than the dark spot in the center of the cavity at $z = z_8$. This is likely caused by the aforementioned Gaussian probe laser that is too large for the simulation box, because it needs to illuminate the complete LWFA. The $z = z_8$ shadowgrams have also been reproduced with the post-processing implementation in section 5.2, indicating that this is of numerical origin from directly within the PIC loop, not from the plugin. It requires further investigations, to fully understand the source of this color change. For example, one can run more simulations with the probe laser extractions at $z_7 < z < z_8$. However, the comparison between the shadowgram, that is virtually propagated from z_7 to z_8 and the shadowgram, that is directly computed at $z = z_8$ also shows, that except for the change of color the general shape and structure of the features is preserved.

Second, the virtual propagation from the extraction plane to $z = z_8$ always looks more similar to the finally propagated shadowgrams than the non-propagated shadowgram, with the exception of the extracted probe laser at $z = z_0$. z_0 is directly mirrored across through the center of the plasma structures from the final position, meaning there are no plasma structures yet that the laser is refracted from. The probe laser, that is propagated with the plugin from $z = z_0$ to $z = z_8$ shows strong ringing effects, whereas the non-propagated image just looks similar to the expected shape of the laser. Thus, the propagation strongly amplifies these ringing artifacts.

Third, the trailing cavities are already faintly visible in the propagated shadowgram that is extracted at $z = z_1$, which lies theoretically just in front of the plasma cavities. This indicates that, although the plasma cavities themselves have the expected width of the plasma wavelength, the plasma modulation around the plasma wake is strong enough to refract the probe laser. This periodic oscillation intensifies for $z = z_2$, when the probe laser directly hits the plasma cavities, and at $z = z_3$ the modulation of the trailing plasma cavities already look similar to the final shadowgram $z = z_8$. Hence, the strongest refraction of the probe laser in the trailing cavities appears, right when the probe laser enters the plasma cavities.

Fourth, the signatures of the leading cavity evolve over a longer time in the shadowgraphy process. The pincer-like shape surrounding the first cavity, is visible at $z = z_4$, in the center of the plasma structures, and becomes clearer and more similar to the final shadowgram over a longer time. It is discussed in section 6.1, that this originates from the non-relativistic bow-shock of the LWFA. This shape is even visible in the unpropagated shadowgrams at $z = z_5$. Lastly, a transverse diffraction structure appears when the probe laser is in the center of the plasma cavities $z = z_4$, especially around and in the first cavity. This feature is visible in both the unpropagated shadowgrams and the propagated shadowgrams,

6.3. Studying the evolution of a single shadowgram from within the plasma wake

although the size of this diffraction appears to increase if the shadowgram is propagated further, which is especially visible at $z = z_5$.

In conclusion, the evolution of different shadowgraphy signatures from an LWFA shadowgram was shown by extracting the probe laser with the in-situ plugin at specific planes within the plasma structures. The final shadowgram signature of the trailing cavities is created when the probe laser enters the plasma wake and hits the density gradients the first time. For the leading cavity, the shadowgraphy signature is mostly determined, when the probe laser is refracted by the density directly in the center of the plasma wake.

7. Outlook and conclusion

7.1. Conclusion

The aim of this thesis was to develop synthetic shadowgraphy diagnostics for the particle-in-cell code PIconGPU. This was successfully achieved with a post-processing implementation according to previous works, that computes synthetic shadowgrams for openPMD conform output files, and an in-situ implementation, which creates the synthetic shadowgrams during simulation runtime. The effects of different shadowgraphy parameters like the numerical aperture, the bandpass-filter and window functions on the resulting shadowgrams were observed with the help of this post-processing code. Afterwards, the post-processing code was utilized to validate the in-situ plugin, which allows to calculate shadowgrams for simulations with much higher resolution for both LWFAs/PWFAs and also near critical density simulations, without having to store and load up to multiple Terabytes of field data.

The novel in-situ plugin was applied for the first time to analyze an LWFA with different object plane positions, probe laser wavelengths and pump probe delays. Furthermore, a different approach of analyzing shadowgrams was shown, where the evolution of a shadowgram was studied by extracting the probe laser directly from within the plasma cavities. This plugin can be used in LWFA and PWFA simulations to provide further insight into experimental shadowgrams, which helps in understanding the physics of the acceleration processes. For example the plugin can be used to identify significant structures in a shadowgram that represent the actual size of the leading cavity.

Supplementary to the direct comparison to the experimental shadowgrams, one can use the in-situ plugin to generate training data with the corresponding charge-density and electric- and magnetic field data outputs for surrogate models. These neural networks might be able to retrieve information about e.g. the actual plasma density and drive laser intensity from the shadowgrams. This would help experiments insofar, that surrogate models could provide a live analysis of the experiment instead of having to wait a longer time for simulation results, which can possibly allow changing crucial experimental parameters during the beam time, thus resulting in more successful experiments.

7.2. Further development

In this work an in-situ shadowgraphy plugin for PIconGPU was presented, and it was shown, that the field extraction and frequency domain Fourier transformation of the plugin computes shadowgrams as expected. Furthermore, it was shown, that changing the object plane, that is the focal position of the virtual imaging system, of the in-situ

7. Outlook and conclusion

Figure 7.1.: The previously shown synthetic shadowgram created with the in-situ plugin from PIconGPU and the corresponding plasma density as line-out plots. The trailing cavities have a longitudinal periodicity equivalent to the plasma wavelength λ_p , however the longitudinal size of the leading cavity δ_y appears much larger in the shadowgram compared to its actual longitudinal size in the plasma density.

plugin works equivalently to the post-processing implementation with minor differences. These differences can be explained by the fact that the plugin time-records the probe pulse, while the post-processing implementation performs a 3D spatial Fourier transform. It is expected, that the time-integrating approach is closer to the actual experimental imaging process inside a CCD.

As next step, the PIconGPU probe laser implementation should be expanded to further reduce numerical artifacts. There is also potential for further performance optimizations, such as parallelizing the calculation of the spatially independent components in the final time domain Fourier transform (eq. (3.15)).

An additional useful feature would be integration planes with arbitrary angles in the simulation box to not restrict the probe laser to the z -axis. This requires a rotational matrix and interpolation to be implemented. It is also interesting to select a polarization orthogonal to the probe laser for measuring the Faraday rotation of the probe pulse.

7.3. Outlook

Compared to the example scenario presented in fig. 7.1, it will be interesting to apply the plugin in further LWFA simulations that are closer to current experiments, mainly with stronger drive lasers and different injection schemes, such as down-ramp or ionization injection. These synthetic shadowgrams can help to better understand experimental shadowgrams. The plugin also does not just extract the probe laser from the simulation, but it can be used to study other radiation in LWFAs, such as the broadband emission that occurs during the electron injection [62].

In experiments, it is known that PWFA shadowgrams generally have significantly different image signatures compared to LWFA shadowgrams [26]. Hence, an obvious next step is to also calculate synthetic PWFA shadowgrams to study the evolution of the shadowgram during the acceleration process but also the individual evolution of single shadowgrams to analyze the physics behind different signatures.

Furthermore, a next step would be to use the scalability of PIConGPU to run larger target normal sheath acceleration (TNSA) simulations and create synthetic shadowgrams for near critical density targets, e.g. hydrogen jet [29]. With the plugin one can study the exact temporal evolution of the plasma density until the target becomes opaque.

A promising application of application of these methods is in studying the general effect of hot plasmas on x-ray lasers. Electromagnetic waves observe the spatial structure and the momentum distribution of the plasma due to the Doppler shift caused by scattering on the electrons. Since the shadowgraphy plugin extracts a laser from a simulation to calculate its energy density on a virtual screen, one can do PIConGPU probing simulations and let the particle-in-cell code apply the phase shifts to the laser, which then in turn might lead to interesting physics, such as color- or intensity-shifts. This can be done with large PIConGPU simulations, that resolve the x-ray propagation.

A. Appendix

A.1. Notation conventions for the different Fourier spaces

For this master's thesis I'll use the following notation conventions to highlight the different Fourier transforms. The time domain Fourier transform is denoted as:

$$\hat{f}(\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int f(t)e^{i\omega t} dt \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$f(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int \hat{f}(\omega)e^{-i\omega t} d\omega, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

the spatial Fourier transform as:

$$\bar{f}(k_x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int f(x)e^{-ik_x x} dx \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int \bar{f}(k_x)e^{ik_x x} dk_x. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

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